

Open Science NL in Its Formative Years

Evaluation Report 2023–2025

March 2026
Dutch Research Council (NWO)

Prof. dr. Paul Wouters (chair)

Noémie Aubert Bonn, PhD.

Henriikka Mustajoki, PhD.

Professor David Sweeney CBE

Robert van der Vooren MSc (secretary)

Table of Content

1	Executive Summary	5
1.1	Main Conclusions	5
1.2	Recommendations	6
2	Guidance for the Reader	7
3	Context and Purpose of the Evaluation	9
3.1	The importance of Open Science in the Netherlands	9
3.2	The purpose and assignment of the evaluation	10
3.3	The global framework: UNESCO's vision on Open Science	10
3.4	Leonelli's vision on Open Science	11
3.5	Complementarity of openness and knowledge safety	11
3.6	How the evaluation committee evaluated OSNL	12
4	Overall evaluation	16
4.1	Key recommendations	16
4.2	OSNL's achievements	16
4.3	Relevance of OSNL initiatives	19
4.4	Coherence of OSNL initiatives	24
4.5	Efficiency	25
4.6	Effectiveness	27
4.7	Sustainability	28
5	Recommendations	32
5.1	Evaluation synthesis	32
5.2	Overview of recommendations and advice	33
	Glossary	37
	List of references	39
	Annex 1: Terms of Reference for the evaluation of Open Science NL	40
1.	Reason for and object of the evaluation	40
2.	Aim and purpose of the evaluation	40
3.	Scope of the evaluation: stakeholders and time period	41
4.	Evaluation questions	41
5.	Basis for assessment: what is the basis for evaluating the object?	41
6.	Workflow	42
7.	Methods	42
8.	Timing, schedule of implementation and budget	42
9.	Use and publication rights	43
10.	Consultation	43
11.	Documentation	43
	Annex 2: Interview guides	44
	Advisory Panels (45 min)	44

Annex 3: List of interviewees	47
Annex 4: Key achievements of Open Science NL in its formative years (2023–2025)	49
1. OSNL as a national catalyst for Open Science.....	49
2. The first work programme (2024–2025)	49
3. The second work programme (2026–2027)	51
4. OSNL self-reflection (2023–2025).....	52
Annex 5: Short biographies of the evaluation committee members.....	55
Paul Wouters (committee chair)	55
David Sweeney	55
Henriikka Mustajoki.....	55
Noémie Aubert Bonn.....	55
Robert van der Vooren (committee secretary)	55

1 Executive Summary

1.1 Main Conclusions

Open Science NL (OSNL) was established within NWO in March 2023 as a temporary national programme office to coordinate and fund initiatives that advance Open Science in the Netherlands. This evaluation examines OSNL's first phase of operation, from March 2023 to June 2025, against the backdrop of the Netherlands' ambition to make Open Science the norm by 2030. As most funded projects are still underway, the evaluation focuses on relevance, coherence, efficiency, early signs of effectiveness, and sustainability.

Open Science Netherlands (OSNL) has delivered a breadth, depth, and pace of action that is exceptional. In less than three years since its March 2023 launch, the organisation has moved decisively from policy aspiration to funded implementation, serving effectively as a catalyst, and building a full, coherent portfolio across infrastructure, capacity building, robust research processes, community empowerment, incentives, and monitoring.

On this basis, the evaluation committee expresses confidence in OSNL's continued leadership to determine the next steps and to succeed with its direction. The evaluation committee can state, without reservation, that OSNL's performance to date is immensely impressive. OSNL merits strong commendation for delivering not just projects, but a working model of national culture change that others in Europe, and beyond, can learn from.

By the end of 2025, approximately 218 projects will have been awarded for a total of €72.4 million, an output level that speaks both to the ambition of the programme and to the trust OSNL has earned across the Dutch research ecosystem. From the outset, OSNL chose a comprehensive interpretation of Open Science that extends well beyond open access to include FAIR data, open research software, and citizen science/societal engagement, the full span of practices that actually change how research is done and shared.

The 2024–2025 work programme translated the NPOS 2030 ambitions into fifteen funding instruments across five clusters, combining technical enablers with human factors. This structure has proven effective in avoiding siloed delivery and creating mutually reinforcing drivers of change, with community building and coordination as distinctive strengths. The 2026–2027 programme reflects a more mature, evidence-informed approach: after a broad initial infrastructure call, OSNL is moving to a more focused round that promotes collaboration, interoperability, and less duplication. Continued support for the Open Science Festival, Open Science Meetings, OSC-NL, and CS-NL has strengthened the national Open Science community and embedded local networks more firmly in the wider movement.

OSNL has widened eligibility to research support staff and ensured that universities of applied sciences (UAS), smaller institutions, and the Caribbean part of the Kingdom could participate meaningfully. These novel funding mechanisms, explicitly recognising non-academic staff, have provided a strong impulse to fundamentally change relationships between non-academic professionals, UAS, and new communities, aligning incentives with real-world labour and helping shift recognition to where the work is done.

OSNL operates in active conversation with the international community, and uses global good practices to inform design choices at home. Its scope and coherence have been publicly recognised, including by the Netherlands Commission for UNESCO, which described OSNL's programme as among the most progressive worldwide, a view endorsed by the evaluation committee.

1.2 Recommendations

The report offers recommendations and advice, grouped by evaluation criteria (chapter 3) and stakeholder (chapter 4).

Key Recommendations:

- Actively implement the new OSNL work programme, maintaining its coherent design and momentum: stay the course.
- Strengthen capacity within the OSNL team to engage further with the community.
- Clarify roles and responsibilities of the different stakeholders in the open science system.
- Promote sustainability beyond impulse funding. Deliver an infrastructure vision.
- Continue to create a research culture that enables and encourages the research community to engage in open science.

These recommendations are developed into advice to relevant stakeholders.

To the OSNL Programme Team

OSNL should stay the course and actively implement the new work programme, maintaining its coherent design and momentum. Continue leading professional communication and prioritise convening as a form of 'people infrastructure' that sustains collaboration. Safeguard OSNL's accumulated social capital and momentum.

Allow justified flexibility to funding eligibility rules where needed. Clarify the different roles, responsibilities, and funding pathways of the various stakeholders in the Dutch Open Science landscape. Support showcasing effectiveness of the OSNL programme, for example through success stories.

To the Steering Board

Continue to be hands-on in mobilising sectors and championing programme needs. Consider reviewing the international relationship of the OSNL programme, particularly with the lens of equity and inclusion.

To the Covenant Partners

Work together to identify the necessary compromises across partners to strengthen implementation and coherence. As far as possible, partners should align incentives, procedures, and expectations, and provide staff with clear guidance for open workflows. Amplify OSNL's goals. Partners act as a bridge between national ambitions and local practice.

Provide protected time for staff, secure funding for coordination roles, and integrate Open Science into strategies and governance. Embedding Open Science requires consistent and practical choices and goes well beyond policy statements.

Clarify responsibilities among Covenant Partners, for recognition-and-rewards, infrastructure stewardship, and skills pipelines to reduce friction between local expectations and national instruments. Commit to long-term support of Open Science to make it sustainable and affirm long-term commitment with structural support.

Coordinate national visions while supporting bottom-up work. Partners should help shape national roadmaps for infrastructure, skills, and community engagement. Help secure long-term funding and clear mandates for the Digital Competence Centres and libraries. Ensure that technical expertise, domain alignment, and interoperability can grow beyond short project cycles.

To NWO

Provide more in-kind support for managing calls so the OSNL team can focus on engagement and coordination.

Ensure that rules and regulations (legislative) as well as NWO policies encourage broader participation in the OSNL programme.

Reconsider co-funding requirements taking in-kind funding and institutional capacity into account. Revisit overhead levels and administrative constraints, including salary-scale rigidity, and learn from OSNL's experience to refine funding instruments that enable mixed teams and community building.

To Knowledge Institutions

Commit to long-term support of Open Science to make it sustainable and affirm long-term commitment with structural support. Embed Open Science in institutional strategies, departmental plans, and leadership expectations. Recognition-and-rewards policies should value open practices consistently across faculties and, where possible, be harmonised between institutions. Provide training to support responsible open research practices (e.g., ethics, integrity, privacy, data stewardship).

Work with OSNL and NWO to ensure fair access to funding schemes and to reduce administrative burdens. Reduce fragmentation by adopting interoperable and sustainable infrastructures, including Digital Competence Centres. Help harmonise policies for responsible data access and sharing.

To Researchers and Research Staff

Embrace the opportunities OSNL creates for shaping the future of research. Engage actively in Open Science Communities and citizen-science initiatives to build networks and skills. Advocate for recognition of open practices within your institutions and contribute to shaping fair assessment systems. Continue to champion open science practices, including FAIR principles.

To Libraries and Library Consortia

Continue to support sustainable, non-profit publishing models, including diamond open access with support from universities and other knowledge institutions. Advance metadata standards, persistent identifiers, and interoperability across institutions. Strengthen Open Science literacy by offering training on topics such as data sharing and open peer review. Host Open Science Communities and support bottom-up activity.

To Research Funders

Funders shape incentives and influence behaviour across the research system. Embed Open Science principles in all calls. Innovate on funding mechanisms to promote collaborations, including with non-academic partners. Align open-science requirements across programmes to ensure clarity and predictability. Recognise open practices to support cultural change.

To Ministries and Parliament

Rebuild and retain Open Science policy expertise within the ministries, expanding its scope to include Open Education. Explore synergies between Open Science and knowledge security to position openness as a strategic asset. Make research systems more resilient by supporting transparent practices and shared standards. These help reveal risks earlier and support coordinated responses.

2 Guidance for the Reader

This document is designed to serve a diverse readership: some will want only the strategic headlines, others will dive into the analytical depth, and many will move back and forth depending on their role, interest, or available time. There is no single correct way to read this report. Instead, consider the structure as a set of interconnected entry points that you can navigate according to your needs.

If you want the essence of the evaluation quickly, start with the Executive Summary and Key Recommendations. These sections contain the main conclusions and proposed actions without requiring you to read the full analysis. They are intentionally concise, but they do not replace the nuance found in the later chapters.

If you wish to understand the reasoning, move from the Key Recommendations to chapters 3 and 4. These sections explain why certain choices were made, what evidence underpins them, and where uncertainties or trade-offs remain. Readers who rely on this document for decision-making, policy development, or strategic alignment will find the necessary depth here.

If you want to understand the bigger picture, the Context and Purpose section provides historically the institutional, and policy foundations that shape the recommendations. These chapters are particularly useful for readers who are new to the topic or who want to understand how the current Open Science landscape and policies emerged.

3 Context and Purpose of the Evaluation

3.1 The importance of Open Science in the Netherlands

Open Science holds a uniquely prominent place in the Netherlands because it builds on long-standing scholarly practices of sharing, collaboration, and public engagement. This tradition also reflects early national science-policy developments. A pivotal moment was the 1974 ‘Nota Wetenschapsbeleid’ (Ministerie van Onderwijs en Wetenschappen, 1974), issued by Boy Trip, Dutch Minister for Research Policy. The memorandum introduced National Research Programmes that oriented the research system toward complex societal challenges and laid foundations for later Dutch leadership in Open Science.

Open Science in the Netherlands aligns with national ambitions to make publicly funded research openly accessible, socially relevant, and internationally competitive. Grassroots initiatives from researchers, libraries, and disciplinary communities laid much of the early groundwork. Momentum was reinforced by the government’s 2014 national mandate for gold open access (Rijksoverheid, 2014), which made the Netherlands one of the first European countries to pursue immediate, publisher-supported openness at scale. Internationally, the Netherlands played a key role when, during its 2016 EU Council Presidency (Council of the European Union, 2016), it championed Council Conclusions on full open access and broader Open Science practices. This political leadership also built on earlier commitments, including the 2004 OECD Declaration on Access to Research Data from Public Funding (OECD, 2004), which emphasized open availability of publicly funded research data and paved the way for the 2006 OECD Recommendation (OECD, 2006) that formalized principles for data sharing.

The Dutch Open Science movement has been driven by a broad coalition of stakeholders. Higher education institutions, research institutes, and university libraries embedded Open Science in their strategies and negotiated transformative agreements. Universities of applied sciences and the Vereniging Hogescholen strengthened practice-based openness, promoted open educational resources, expanded access through the HBO-Kennisbank, and embedded openness in lectorates and knowledge circles. Many universities also appointed Open Science Ambassadors, supporting coordination of implementation across institutions. Public funders such as NWO and ZonMw made open access and data stewardship core funding requirements, while SURF and the Royal Library provided national technical infrastructure. The sector’s cultural agenda, articulated in ‘Ruimte voor ieders talent’ (VSNU, NFU, KNAW, NWO, ZonMw, 2019) linked Open Science with recognition and rewards and a more collaborative research culture. The Nationale Wetenschapsagenda (Tweede Kamer der Staten-Generaal, 2015) further emphasized societal engagement and collective knowledge creation.

National coordination under the National Open Science Programme (NPOS) I and II brought these actors together. NPOS I 2017–2020 (Nationaal Programma Open Science, 2017) mobilized the sector around shared ambitions: full open access, FAIR data stewardship, and citizen science. It also created initial governance structures. NPOS II 2021–2024 (Nationaal Programma Open Science, 2021) shifted toward implementation, launched concrete programmes, strengthened national infrastructure, and supported cultural change, including alignment with the ‘recognition & rewards’ movement. A key innovation was the ‘Ambition document and rolling agenda’, which strengthened long-term strategic coordination.

As Open Science activities expanded, a temporary project-based model was no longer sufficient. This led to the establishment of Open Science NL (OSNL) under the Dutch Research Council NWO governance in 2023, designed to ensure long-term coordination, stable funding, and system-wide alignment.

This evaluation of OSNL takes place within this broader, long-standing multi-stakeholder effort to ensure that openness enhances research quality, integrity, and societal value of research across the Netherlands.

3.2 The purpose and assignment of the evaluation

The evaluation of OSNL occurs within a context of significant national investment and policy ambition. In 2022, the Dutch Ministry of Education, Culture and Science committed €184 million over ten years to accelerate the transition to Open Science, aiming to make it the norm across Dutch research by 2030. NWO was tasked with managing these funds and providing programme governance, acting as chair of the Open Science Covenant partners, a coalition of 16 organisations spanning universities, university medical centres, universities of applied science, libraries, and research funders. This governance model combines strategic oversight with operational delivery, ensuring sector-wide collaboration while maintaining institutional autonomy.

OSNL was formally established within NWO in March 2023 as a temporary unit to coordinate and fund initiatives that advance Open Science practices. Its activities are guided by the Covenant (Ministerie van Onderwijs, Cultuur en Wetenschap, 2023) and structured through multi-year work programmes aligned with the Netherlands National Open Science Programme (NPOS) 2030 (Nationaal Programma Open Science, 2022). The first OSNL programme (2024–2025) focused on building foundational capacity, infrastructure, and community engagement, while the second (2026–2027) pivots toward consolidation and sustainability. National government-wide budget reductions in 2023 resulted in OSNL budget reductions by 50% from 2025 onwards. NWO absorbed most cuts internally, limiting the effective reduction to 10% and safeguarding programme continuity. A target of €17–19 million for 2026 reflects strong institutional commitment and NWO's flexibility in maintaining momentum.

The purpose of this evaluation, as stipulated in Article 8 of the Covenant and detailed in the Terms of Reference (Annex 1), is to assess OSNL's functioning during its formative phase (March 2023–June 2025). This period represents a start-up phase in which most funded projects are still in implementation, making it premature to measure long-term impact. Accordingly, the evaluation focuses on four criteria, relevance, coherence, efficiency, sustainability (added by the evaluation committee), and early indicators of effectiveness, providing insight for NWO, the Ministry, OSNL itself, and Covenant partners. The findings will inform strategic decisions on programme direction, resource allocation, and governance, and will be presented to Parliament as part of the government's accountability framework.

This chapter situates the evaluation within its broader (inter)national context, clarifies its objectives and scope, and outlines the rationale for the chosen criteria. It also frames the evaluation against the cultural and systemic change OSNL seeks to achieve: embedding open access to research outputs and sustainable infrastructures, fostering citizen science participation, and reforming research assessment and recognition systems. These ambitions are not without challenges, ensuring long-term funding beyond stimulus grants, sustaining institutional engagement after programme funding ends, and managing tensions between traditional research practices and Open Science ideals. Emerging issues such as the ethical and practical implications of AI further underscore the need for adaptive strategies. Against this backdrop, the evaluation aims to provide a balanced, evidence-informed assessment of OSNL's progress and its capacity to deliver on the national vision for Open Science.

3.3 The global framework: UNESCO's vision on Open Science

The international context for Open Science is shaped by UNESCO's Recommendation on Open Science (UNESCO, 2021). This instrument provides a globally endorsed framework for countries and institutions, defining Open Science as an inclusive paradigm that:

- makes multilingual scientific knowledge openly available, accessible, and reusable;
- expands collaboration and information sharing for the benefit of science and society;
- opens the processes of knowledge creation, evaluation, and communication to societal actors beyond the traditional scientific community.

The Recommendation emphasizes that Open Science spans all disciplines, natural sciences, social sciences, and the humanities, and rests on five interlocking pillars: open scientific knowledge; Open Science infrastructures; science communication; open engagement of societal actors; and open dialogue with other knowledge systems, including indigenous and local knowledge. It calls for immediate open access to publications and a wide range of research outputs, prepared in timely, human- and machine-readable formats and curated for long-term preservation. It advocates for community-governed, non-commercial, interoperable platforms and repositories, persistent identifiers, and federated computing and data storage designed around FAIR and CARE principles.

Importantly, UNESCO balances openness with responsibility: access should be “as open as possible” yet “as closed as necessary,” with proportionate restrictions for privacy, national security, intellectual property, and sacred or secret indigenous knowledge. These commitments are anchored in core values, quality and integrity, collective benefit, equity and fairness, diversity and inclusiveness, and guiding principles such as transparency, reproducibility, and sustainability. For implementation, UNESCO outlines seven areas of action for Member States, from enabling policies and infrastructure investment to capacity building and international cooperation, complemented by monitoring mechanisms that capture both intended and unintended effects.

This breadth and legitimacy explain why the Recommendation served as a meaningful reference for OSNL and repeatedly surfaced among interviewees during this evaluation.

3.4 Leonelli’s vision on Open Science

While UNESCO provides a normative baseline, Sabina Leonelli’s *Philosophy of Open Science* (2023) offers a critical lens on how openness is understood and enacted, and resonates strongly with the evaluation committee’s ambition to assess real cultural change rather than rely on administrative proxies. Leonelli argues that contemporary practice often treats openness primarily as unlimited sharing of research objects, papers, datasets, code, placing “transparency first” and expecting quality and inclusion to follow. This object-oriented view, she contends, can unintentionally constrain epistemic diversity, worsen epistemic injustice, and undermine reliability.

Leonelli proposes reframing openness as judicious connection: forging inclusive, context-sensitive relations among researchers and communities operating within diverse systems of practice. Policies that ignore these differences risk flattening pluralism and privileging dominant repertoires. Her analysis of cases such as SARS-CoV-2 genomic data sharing and crop data linkage illustrates how prioritising speed and unqualified transparency can sideline equity and contextual expertise, reducing reliability. She cautions against techno-administrative capture, where the over-reliance on prescribed tools and procedures may drift from supporting reflexive practice to constraining creativity, and recommends investing in communities of practice, micro-collaboration, and balanced digital and analogue exchanges.

Leonelli’s perspective inverts the common “direction of travel”: effective Open Science should begin with inclusion and justice, then address quality, and only then pursue transparency, ensuring openness is meaningful and trustworthy. This emphasis on inclusion and situated judgment aligns closely with the evaluation committee’s evaluative stance: measuring success through evidence of systemic change, capacity, and pluralism, not through compliance checklists or superficial metrics.

3.5 Complementarity of openness and knowledge safety

The Netherlands holds a distinctive and internationally recognised position in Open Science. This position is the result of long-standing commitment from researchers, institutions, funders, and policymakers. National coordination has advanced open access, FAIR data stewardship, and reforms in research assessment. Dutch actors have also shaped European and global discussions on Open Science.

In parallel, the Dutch research system has developed a proportionate and governance-oriented approach to knowledge safety and security. This approach reflects the country's highly internationalised research environment and its exposure to risks such as dual-use research, strategically sensitive technologies, and uneven international reciprocity. Dutch policy allows actors to view knowledge security as part of responsible research governance, emphasising proportionality, institutional responsibility, and clear accountability.

The evaluation committee observes that these two agendas, Open Science and Knowledge Security, are often viewed as being in tension. The committee's view, however, is that they can reinforce each other. Implementing Open Science at scale in the Netherlands has required strong capabilities in transparency, robust data stewardship, governance design, incentive alignment, and cultural change. These same capabilities are also essential for credible and proportionate approaches to knowledge safety. Practices such as differentiated openness, contextual decision-making, and sustained engagement with researchers can strengthen security rather than undermine it.

In the committee's assessment, openness is not a vulnerability but an enabler of intentionality, trust and resilience in research. Embedding knowledge-safety considerations within established frameworks for research integrity helps prevent over-correction and avoids unnecessary barriers to collaboration. It also supports responsible international engagement. The evaluation committee therefore sees a strategic opportunity to link Open Science expertise more explicitly with actors in the knowledge security domain. Joint guidance, shared training, and coordinated frameworks can support a coherent approach and reinforce the resilience and international credibility of the Dutch research system.

3.6 How the evaluation committee evaluated OSNL

For the OSNL evaluation, UNESCO and Leonelli provide complementary reference points that shaped both the conceptual framework and the practical methodology. UNESCO offers a globally endorsed structure and policy levers for Open Science, while Leonelli supplies a diagnostic lens to assess whether OSNL's approach strengthens equity and pluralism rather than reinforcing existing hierarchies. This alignment resonates strongly with the evaluation committee's ambition to measure real cultural change rather than rely on administrative proxies.

The evaluation process began with an orientation phase to establish a shared understanding of the assignment, clarify the framework, and agree on the work plan. Evidence collection combined document analysis, semi-structured interviews, a two-day site visit, and participation in the Open Science Festival, enabling triangulation across sources and perspectives. An evaluation matrix guided inquiry, comprising main questions, indicative sub-questions, and potential data sources for each criterion, ensuring transparency and consistency.

The analysis was structured around five criteria: relevance, coherence, efficiency, early indicators of effectiveness, and sustainability. The first four criteria were drawn from the Terms of Reference for the evaluation, while sustainability was introduced by the evaluation committee in early discussions to reflect OSNL's strategic role in driving systemic change. This criterion examines whether OSNL's design and implementation create conditions for resilience, financial continuity, institutional commitment, governance clarity, and cultural normalisation, and its capacity to anticipate future challenges such as new technologies and political changes.

3.6.1 Appointment of the evaluation committee

The Evaluation Committee members were selected to encompass complementary areas of Open Science, of the research lifecycle, and of the sectors responsible for systemic changes in support of Open Science. Members were selected from discussions between the Steering Board and the OSNL Team, aiming to identify experts who were independent from OSNL to minimise conflicting interests. Selected members were invited via email by the OSNL team, after which a committee Chair was identified and a secretary support was provided by

NWO. After acceptance of the evaluation by committee members, all relations and contacts took place through the committee secretariat.

3.6.2 Selected committee members

The committee is composed of Prof. dr. Paul Wouters (chair), Noémie Aubert Bonn, PhD, Henriikka Mustajoki, PhD, and Professor David Sweeney CBE. The secretariat role was fulfilled by Robert van der Vooren, who also contributed to the evaluation through his professional experience.

3.6.3 Generative AI statement

The committee confirms that its use of generative artificial intelligence was limited, transparent, and implemented in a manner consistent with the principles of the NWO policy on generative AI. The committee is an independent external body that did not perform applicant assessments or make funding decisions. Its remit focused on evaluating the structure, functioning, and outcomes of the OSNL programme rather than assessing individual proposals. Because the NWO policy is primarily written to govern assessment and review processes involving applicants and confidential proposals, the committee's operational context differs from the assessment context that the policy mainly addresses. Nevertheless, the committee has deliberately connected its practice to the NWO policy and has adopted the policy's core safeguards where suitable.

Generative AI was used only for low risk, non-content sensitive tasks, specifically:

- Transcription of recorded committee meetings using Microsoft Teams transcription features.
- Summarisation of those transcriptions using Microsoft Copilot to produce draft summaries for editorial use.
- Summarisation of reference documentation, for example to detect potential missed information.

All substantive analysis, judgements, and recommendations in this report were developed, debated, and finalised exclusively by committee members without AI assistance.

3.6.4 Evaluation process

Table 1 details the diverse phases and actions taken by the evaluation committee members throughout the evaluation process. As can be seen, evidence collected for the final report included publicly available documents such as information detailed on the OSNL website, the OSNL Work Programmes, NPOS 2030, and additional documents identified as relevant as the evaluation progressed. The evidence also included embargoed documents, first-hand reflections from informal discussions with the Open Science Festival 2025 participants, and semi-structured group interviews with selected stakeholders to understand personal perspectives and recommendations for the coming years of OSNL.

Date	Phase and action	Evidence collected
Summer 2025	Appointment - Selection of the evaluation committee and invitations.	N/A
July 2025	Orientation - Initial meeting of the evaluation committee (online) to familiarise the committee with the assignment and decide on ways of working.	Available online documents including: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – OSNL Website – OSNL Work Programme 2023-2025 – NPOS 2030

Date	Phase and action	Evidence collected
Sept 2025	Orientation - Online meeting of the evaluation committee to define the workplan for the evaluation.	Document shared with the evaluation committee OSNL Self-Evaluation
Oct 2025	Documentation - First in-person meeting of the evaluation committee to give an overview of available documents, identify questions that need to be addressed in interviews, and plan for conducting the interviews.	N/A
Oct 2025	Documentation - Open Science Festival which allowed the evaluation committee members to identify successes, challenges, and potential blind spots of the OSNL programme.	Colloquial input from discussions with Festival participants
Nov 2025	Documentation - Online meeting of the evaluation committee to finalise interview guides.	OSNL Work Programme 2025-2027
Nov 2025	Site Visit - Three-day in-person meeting which included two full days of interviews with stakeholders and one day of evidence consolidation.	Interview data
Dec 2025 - Jan 2026	Reporting - The secretariat provided a first draft of the report which was revised by the evaluation committee members in two online meetings and multiple rounds of feedback and edits.	Additional documents mentioned in interviews and site visit (referenced)
Jan 2026	Reporting - 1.5 day in-person meeting to finalise the report.	N/A

Table 1. Overview of the phases (in bold) and actions that led to the evaluation.

Interviews targeted a broad array of stakeholders that were agreed as relevant by the evaluation committee. The interviews were extensively prepared with detailed interview guides (Annex 2), based on OSNL's self-reflection, the Terms of Reference, and the committee's knowledge of national and international open science programmes and practices.

Interviewees included (i) the Director of OSNL Hans de Jonge; (ii) seven representatives of the OSNL Steering Board; (iii) six early career researchers who were involved or interested in Open Science initiatives; (iv) six representatives of OSNL advisory panels; (v) six representatives of the covenant partners (Bestuurlijk Overleg); (vi) fourteen funding recipients from OSNL projects, spanning across Open Science Communities, Recognising and Rewarding Open Science, Netherland's University Press, and Digital Competence Centres; (vii) four members of the OSNL internal team; and (viii) two unfunded applicants. Interviewees' names are included in Annex 3. In order to preserve anonymity, we agreed that quotes would only refer to the interviewee groups, unless otherwise specified with interviewees.

Before interviews took place, the evaluation committee discussed the areas that would be important to address to inform the evaluation. To do this, in the first in-person meeting of the evaluation committee, committee members discussed a list of initial questions based on the information they found missing or insufficient in the documents and material available (i.e., the OSNL Website, the OSNL Work Programme 2023-2025, NPOS 2030, and the OSNL Self-Evaluation). The resulting questions were organised into an evaluation matrix around the five pillars of relevance, coherence, efficiency, early indicators of effectiveness, and sustainability.

After this initial brainstorm, a few members of the evaluation committee with experience of large language models inputted available documentation and the evaluation matrix in a closed AI tool to capture any information that may have been missed but that provided insight on the selected questions capture any information that may have been missed but that provided insight on the selected questions in the available documentation and to build inspiration on how the questions could be formulated to capture richer responses.

A selection of questions from the resulting inspiration questions were then carefully edited, adapted, and assigned to interview groups based on the expected relevance of the interviewees in answering the questions. In doing so, a thorough interview guide was composed for each interview group, ensuring that the questions, topics, and formulation was fit for the knowledge and experience of the target group. All interview guides were revised by the evaluation committee members, and each committee member agreed to lead a few interviews to maximise a balanced chairing and minimise biases that could be generated by chairing patterns.

Interview participants were contacted via emails sent from OSNL secretariat, except for Early Career Researchers who were contacted by the early career representative member in the evaluation committee. Interviews were all conducted in person in Den Haag during the site visit except the interview with unfunded applicants which had to be moved to a later date to accommodate for availability and was conducted online. Interviews were recorded and automatically transcribed using Microsoft Teams.

After the in-person interviews were completed, evaluation committee members spent a day discussing their impressions and consolidating evidence. The resulting impressions were used as a baseline for structuring the evaluation report. The evaluation report was drafted by the evaluation committee secretariat and revised in rounds of reviews and meetings between the evaluation committee secretariat and the evaluation committee members from December 2025 to February 2026.

4 Overall evaluation

This chapter synthesises evidence from stakeholder interviews, document review, and the programme’s own self-reflection to offer a balanced assessment of OSNL. The evaluation starts by providing a broad appreciation of OSNL’s achievements. We appreciated OSNL’s self-reflection as highly informative and self-critical. A more detailed reading of the self-reflection by the committee can be found in Annex 4.

The section on OSNL’s achievements follows with a list of observations and considerations directed at different stakeholders. The narrative distinguishes factual observations from interpretive considerations: observations are drawn from the material and data collected, and considerations indicate how those observations may inform decision-making and future programming.

Where informative, the committee added illustrative quotes from the interviews and site visit.

Advice by the evaluation committee follows the observations and considerations.

4.1 Key recommendations

Based on the observations, considerations, and document review made throughout this evaluation, the evaluation committee proposes five key recommendations they consider relevant.

1. Actively implement the new work programme, maintaining its coherent design and momentum: stay the course.
2. Strengthen capacity within the OSNL team to engage further with the community.
3. Clarify roles and responsibilities of the different stakeholders in the Open Science system.
4. Promote sustainability beyond impulse funding. Deliver an infrastructure vision.
5. Continue to create a research culture that enables and encourages the research community to engage in Open Science.

4.2 OSNL’s achievements

OSNL has delivered a breadth, depth, and pace of action that the evaluation committee considered exceptional. In less than three years since its March 2023 launch, the organisation has moved decisively from policy aspiration to funded implementation, serving effectively as a catalyst, and building a full, coherent portfolio across infrastructure, capacity building, robust research processes, community empowerment, incentives, and monitoring.

By backing pragmatic, implementable initiatives that create “boots on the ground,” OSNL has stimulated political and organisational change through practice, embedding a reflexive approach that learns from the field and rapidly iterates. By the end of 2025, approximately 218 projects will have been awarded for a total of €72.4 million, an output level that speaks both to the ambition of the programming and to the trust OSNL has earned across the Dutch research ecosystem.

From the outset, OSNL chose a comprehensive interpretation of Open Science that extends well beyond open access to include FAIR data, open research software, and citizen science/societal engagement, the full span of practices that actually change how research is done and shared

The first work programme (2024–2025) translated the NPOS 2030 ambitions into fifteen concrete funding instruments, structured across five clusters that address both technical enablers and human factors. This architecture has proven highly effective: it avoids siloed delivery and instead creates mutually reinforcing levers

of culture change, capacity, infrastructure, communities, incentives, and evidence, with strong community building and coordination as a distinctive hallmark so that progress in one area enables progress in the next.

The second work programme (2026–2027) then promises to strengthen this design by making the mapping to culture change even more explicit, ensuring that every euro invested advances: “make it possible,” “make it easy,” “make it normative,” “make it rewarding,” and “make it required” (Nosek, 2019).

The programme office has transformed a national policy vision into operational instruments with impressive velocity. Within the first cycle alone, OSNL launched and ran competitive calls (e.g., Open Science Infrastructure, Replication Studies), non-competitive calls (e.g., Strengthening DCCs, Recognising & Rewarding Open Science), tendered strategic assignments (Monitoring & Evaluation pilot) and direct grants to stabilise keystone communities (OSC-NL and CS-NL). This diversity of mechanisms is not an administrative effect but a deliberate and effective way to match instrument form to field needs, thereby lowering barriers to participation and accelerating uptake. Interviews clearly highlighted that the OSNL team is widely regarded as top experts in Open Science who are reachable and responsive and whose engagement has reinforced confidence and accelerated adoption. The evaluation committee noted the empirical footprint visible in the numbers of instruments launched, projects funded, panels convened, events delivered, and communities reached, demonstrating organisational discipline and a rare ability to move the system from deliberation to delivery.

OSNL’s portfolio consistently identifies and unblocks system bottlenecks. The National Training Platform for Research Data Professionals and the expansion of DCC capacity (trainers, community managers, ontology/metadata expertise, and national coordination at the eScience Center) tackle the chronic skills deficit that otherwise holds back FAIR and reusable research. The Research Software Sustainability programme addresses a historic blind spot by recognising maintenance and community-driven enhancement as first-class research contributions, thus improving the reproducibility and longevity of software-based research. The Replication Studies programme, revived and broadened, injects methodological rigor across disciplines and normalises verification as part of scholarly practice. These are not isolated interventions: they interlock by design, so that training enables infrastructure use, infrastructure supports robust methods, and incentives reward the behaviours OSNL wants to see. Alongside these, the tDCCs have functioned as an important additional element of change, linking domain-specific expertise to national coordination, and helping align infrastructure, skills, and governance.

The evaluation committee considered the 2026–2027 programme to show mature, evidence-informed targeting. After a deliberately broad 2024–2025 infrastructure call (which usefully surfaced the full range of needs), OSNL pivots to a more focused infrastructure round with an explicit success-rate goal ($\geq 25\%$), encouraging collaboration and interoperability and reducing duplication. Two further moves are especially commendable. First, the sensitive data initiative pairs national coordination with 28 implementation grants, exactly the kind of balanced, co-designed approach required to harmonise policy and practice in a legally and ethically complex domain. Second, the Making Research Outputs FAIR micro-grants democratises improvement: small, nimble funds convert latent value in legacy datasets, essential software, hardware designs, and AI models into widely reusable assets, while requiring recipients to document and share lessons learned. Both instruments maximize return on investment by amplifying community effort and accelerating re-use.

OSNL’s sustained support for the Open Science Festival and Open Science Meetings has created an annual rhythm and a local cadence where practitioners meet peers, surface needs, compare practice, and co-create solutions. Stabilising OSC-NL and CS-NL with targeted, time-bound funding has professionalised the connective tissue of the movement, ensuring that local communities are not only active but embedded and networked nationally. The Citizen Science Hubs bring societal engagement into the institutional mainstream, while the 2027 mentoring round compounds learning by pairing established hubs with new ones, an elegant way to scale without diluting quality. Interviews revealed a clear positive response from funded communities who report

feeling listened to and reflected in the new Work Programme. This appreciation underscores OSNL's responsiveness and the legitimacy of its direction. Together, these choices foster peer-to-peer diffusion and make Open Science behaviours visible, valued, and normal.

OSNL widened eligibility to research support staff and ensured that universities of applied sciences, smaller institutions, philosophical universities, and the Caribbean part of the Kingdom could participate meaningfully. These novel ways of funding mechanisms, explicitly recognising non-academic staff, have provided a strong impulse to fundamentally change relationships between non-academic professionals, UAS, and new communities, aligning incentives with real-world labour and helping shift recognition to where the work is done. Feedback collected through OSNL's self-reflection underlines how empowering this has been in practice and was appreciated by the evaluation committee.

OSNL operates in active conversation with the international community, through CoNOSC, CoARA, RDA, ReSA, EOSC, and ORE, and uses global good practices (e.g., POSI, Invest in Open Infrastructure pilots) to inform design choices at home. Its scope and coherence have been publicly recognised, including by the Netherlands Commission for UNESCO, which described OSNL's programme as among the most progressive worldwide, a view endorsed by the evaluation committee. This positioning matters: it enables the Netherlands to contribute to, not merely adopt, global standards and to benefit from the efficiencies of shared learning and interoperability across borders.

OSNL has maintained the 6% overhead cap, leveraged NWO's established processes and shared services, and adopted instrument types that minimise applicant burden where appropriate (e.g., non-competitive calls and rolling micro-grants), while using competitive and tender procedures where they add value. The resulting pattern is both cost-conscious and fit-for-purpose. Success rates in the first cycle reflect intelligent scoping: Citizen Science Hubs were calibrated for "front-runners" (hence a higher success rate), Replication Studies call sits near NWO's healthy target band, and the infrastructure call was intentionally inclusive to map demand and inform the second cycle's targeted round. The evaluation committee considered this to be exemplary portfolio stewardship.

Many national programmes monitor outputs, while OSNL chose to monitor change. Commissioning a national monitoring and evaluation framework (CWTS & Dialogic) that blends quantitative indicators with qualitative insights into behaviour, barriers, and practices shows methodological sophistication and a commitment to learning. The emphasis on an inclusive process and an online prototype dashboard lays the groundwork for transparent, evidence-based course-correction across the decade.

When the Ministry's decision halved OSNL's budget, the programme did not retrench to minimalism. Instead, OSNL re-optimized its portfolio with the considerable support of NWO's structural compensation. It protected high-leverage community and capacity instruments. It introduced nimble grants that convert small funds into large, reusable value. It also concentrated system-level efforts where national coordination is indispensable, such as sensitive data and infrastructure sustainability.

This calm and strategic response to an external shock shows institutional maturity and sound risk management. It also demonstrates the strength of NWO's commitment: NWO acted decisively to safeguard continuity, buffer volatility, and enable OSNL to stay focused on its mission rather than its constraints. The evaluation committee commended NWO's supportive role.

Across both work programmes, OSNL's core achievement is to treat Open Science as a system, not a slogan. It invests in the people who make openness feasible, the infrastructures that make it possible, the incentives that make it rewarding, the communities that make it normative, and the policies and monitoring that make it required, all at once. By joining up these levers, and by sequencing them from broad foundation (2024–2025) to targeted consolidation (2026–2027), OSNL has significantly increased the probability that Open Science will outlast project cycles and become the everyday fabric of Dutch research.

On this basis, the evaluation committee expresses confidence in OSNL's continued leadership to determine the next steps and to succeed with its direction. The evaluation committee can state, without reservation, that OSNL's performance to date is immensely impressive. Few programmes manage to be as ambitious in scope, as precise in execution, and as responsive to community needs, all while navigating a challenging financial environment and setting a high bar for international alignment and accountability. Stakeholders interviewed for the evaluation unequivocally confirmed this observation, applauding OSNL for its achievements, complete involvement in moving Open Science forward, reachability and approachability to individuals from all different communities, roles, and seniority levels, and absolute dedication into its cause. OSNL merits strong commendation for delivering not just projects, but a working model of national culture change that others in Europe, and beyond, can learn from.

4.3 Relevance of OSNL initiatives

The interviews reinforced the perspective that the impact of Open Science extends well beyond research work. Open Science was described as a prerequisite to rigorous science and to science that reaches society, reinforcing the crucial importance of giving Open Science a place of priority on the national agenda.

“The culture that now exists in academia is unfit for the work that we do, the position that we have in society. It doesn't serve society and Open Science is one way – probably the way – to create accountability. The ability to create transparency to make sure that people, everybody, society, understands why research and education in higher institutions is so important. And right now we're just busy counting beans.”

Funded applicant OS Communities and Publishing

OSNL's portfolio aligns closely with the ambitions articulated in the National Plan Open Science 2030 (NPOS 2030) and with international frameworks such as UNESCO's Recommendation on Open Science and the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). Funding for Digital Competence Centres (DCCs), citizen-science hubs, and recognition-and-rewards pilots reflects a systemic reading of the transition, addressing skills, infrastructure, and incentives together. Interviewees acknowledged OSNL's catalytic role in initiating cultural change and in turning national aspirations into operational instruments.

Observation on inclusiveness:

Regarding inclusiveness, interviewees stressed that OSNL is unique in its approach which organically includes all relevant parties, providing a reach at the systemic level and making Open Science accessible across research communities. This inclusive approach was mentioned as a great strength and essential to creating genuine impact and building shared changes and solutions.

*“What I appreciate in the way of working with Open Science NL is that it's not only focusing on researchers, but on the whole field. [...] It's hard work and it takes endurance and persistence. [...] What I really value in the initiative of Open Science is that **all the parties are involved**”*

OSNL steering Board

At the same time, interviews surfaced nuances in perceived relevance across the sector. “Stakeholder representation” was one recurrent theme. In line with OSNL's self-reflection (2023–2025), smaller institutions and universities of applied sciences reported that their priorities, often emphasising societal engagement and practice-oriented outcomes alongside technical compliance, were not always visible in national conversations.

Observation on barriers for participation:

While interviewees recognised the important role of OSNL in opening opportunities for new communities, especially to universities of applied sciences and to research staff, several applicants described practical barriers for civil-society organisations, which are key actors in grassroots citizen science.

Consideration:

More opportunities for the diversity of partners would increase the inclusiveness and relevance of consortia without compromising accountability.

Advice:

Ensure that rules and regulations (legislative) as well as NWO policies encourage broader participation in the OSNL programme.

With respect to emerging themes, stakeholders asked for a clear stance on the responsible use of Artificial Intelligence and on digital sovereignty. The addition of AI in the 2026-2027 OSNL programme shows that OSNL is forward looking and was welcomed by interviewees, but further considerations were voiced.

Observation on emerging themes:

Artificial Intelligence and digital sovereignty are important emerging themes, that are increasingly intertwined with openness and knowledge security.

Consideration:

Articulating principles that treat openness and security as complementary will help OSNL and partners navigate these challenges. A resilient Open Science system will need principles that can absorb technological shocks and geopolitical shifts without compromising its core values. Such principles will support OSNL in maintaining mission coherence while adapting to a rapidly changing technological and geopolitical landscape.

Advice:

Explore synergies between Open Science and knowledge security to position openness as a strategic asset.

Observation on Open Education:

The scope of the programme that was set by the ministry was described as limiting by some interviewees given its disregard for Open Education as one of its core elements of focus.

Consideration:

While Open Education was explicitly recognised in earlier national policy, such as the Strategic Agenda for Higher Education and Research 2015–2025 (Ministerie van Onderwijs, Cultuur en Wetenschap, 2015), recent OCW documents no longer articulate a continued framework for it. To strengthen policy coherence, the ministry could clarify how Open Education fits into its post-2025 vision for open knowledge. Given the end of the Open and Online Education scheme, a renewed policy stance would help prevent fragmentation and provide institutions with the stability needed to sustain open educational practices.

Advice:

Rebuild and retain Open Science policy expertise within the ministries, expanding its scope to include Open Education.

Finally, several interviewees pointed to areas where continued, targeted investment would be beneficial.

Observation on new challenges:

New challenges in the domain of diamond open access and open research hardware remain priorities for development, and valorisation and societal impact are unevenly embedded across instruments.

Consideration:

Maintaining attention to these themes will strengthen bibliodiversity, affordability, and the connection between research and society.

Advice:

- Continue leading professional communication and prioritise convening as a form of ‘people infrastructure’ that sustains collaboration.
- Continue to support sustainable, non-profit publishing models, including diamond open access with support from universities and other knowledge institutions. Libraries are essential to knowledge stewardship and open-access publishing.

4.3.1 Balance between collaboration and competition

Design choices in funding instruments shape who can participate and what kinds of collaborations form.

Observation on coordination:

Interviewees also showed appreciation for the ‘match-making events’ organised in anticipation of competitive calls. They considered those useful in fostering coordination, collaboration, and complementary proposals. However, interviewees noted that broad competitive infrastructure calls, if not paired with coordination, can fragment effort and produce short-lived solutions.

Interviewees, in particular applicants (both funded and unfunded) praised non-competitive mechanisms, such as recognition-and-rewards support, for enabling institutional change where competition adds little value.

[The Open Science Communities call] “was a non competitive call, which was really great. All communities could apply for it. You just created a plan and I really like the fact that they basically trusted us with the money [...] they trusted us to know what would be most beneficial to the community that we were evolving. So I really like that one.”

Funded applicant

Consideration:

Encouraging consortia-based approaches and coordinated scopes in infrastructure funding reduces duplication, raises interoperability, and improves sustainability. Continuing to promote ‘match-making events,’ and ensuring that these events are advertised and open to all, would help support coordinated scope and collaboration.

Advice:

Continue leading professional communication and prioritise convening as a form of ‘people infrastructure’ that sustains collaboration.

Observation on fair competition:

Interviewees praised the ‘one partner, one application’ rule as an effective way to spread opportunity and avoid concentration and unfair competition.

“I absolutely love the way that competition is actively being tried to reduce <sic> within the programme so collaborations are encouraged. People are discouraged from being in multiple applications. And then there are possibilities. Also facilitation from Open Science NL to bring people together, like when there is an information session. [...] So I think that's a very, very positive thing that is happening now.”

Unfunded applicant

Consideration:

However, it was clear from interviewees that in specific cases where expertise is scarce for institutions e.g. Universities of Applied Sciences, this rule strengthened scarcity of expertise in areas where it may be most needed.

Advice:

- Allow justified flexibility to funding eligibility rules where needed
- Work with OSNL and NWO to ensure fair access to funding schemes and to reduce administrative burdens.

Observation on broadening participation:

Participants mentioned that OSNL could be an ideal testing ground for innovative review methods. For example, for small, early-stage public-engagement ideas, lotteries among eligible proposals were mentioned as a possible way to reduce marginal scoring disputes, an element that was observed by unfunded applicants, and broaden participation.

Several interviewees, especially applicants (funded and unfunded) and early career researchers supported introducing lotteries and perceived OSNL to be a fitting site for experimental funding mechanism.

“Open Science NL should also provide room for alternatives to [...] decisions based on hierarchies and rankings and so forth. [...] It's the complete opposite direction from going towards a responsible open governance. It would be great if that's possible [...] A move towards a lottery, combining it with a PPP [preliminary project proposal] review [...] And combine it with open proposals.”

Early Career Researchers

Consideration:

Using such pragmatic mechanisms selectively complements formal peer-review for larger, more complex calls.

Advice:

Continue leading professional communication and prioritise convening as a form of ‘people infrastructure’ that sustains collaboration.

4.3.2 Cultural change and sustainability

Impulse funding has successfully generated momentum, yet long-term embedding depends on structural integration within institutional strategies and national frameworks.

Observation on making openness the norm:

Early career researchers and support staff emphasised that open practices often require additional effort without corresponding recognition. Such misalignment reinforces the perception that openness is voluntary, unrewarded, or even professionally risky.

Consideration:

Cultural uptake is strengthened when incentive structures reflect and support open practices. Coordinated efforts across Human Resources, recognition-and-reward frameworks, and institutional policies could help reduce perceived risks and encourage researchers at all stages to adopt more open ways of working.

“Open Science feels like an extra burden unless it is integrated into recognition and reward systems.”

Early Career Researchers

Advice:

- Value Open Science and open practices in recognition-and-rewards policies consistently across faculties and, where possible, harmonise recognition-and-rewards policies between institutions.
- Advocate for recognition of open practices within your institutions and contribute to shaping fair assessment systems.

Observation on recognition and rewards:

Among interviewees it was noted that cultural change has been strongest where Open Science Communities or support structures already existed, while smaller institutions, universities of applied sciences, and civil-society actors often face more barriers to involvement. Some coordinators cautioned that such communities tend to attract the believers, leading to uneven participation.

Consideration:

Addressing uneven cultural reach benefits from engagement approaches that explicitly recognise differences in capacity, organisational structure, and local contexts. Inclusive consultation, attention to underrepresented groups, and outreach tailored to diverse institutional realities can help distribute cultural change more equitably across the research ecosystem.

Advice:

- Allow justified flexibility to funding eligibility rules where needed
- Work with OSNL and NWO to ensure fair access to funding schemes and to reduce administrative burdens.

Observation on sustainability:

Interviewees consistently described the early phase of the programme as energising. At the same time, they noted that such cultural shifts remain vulnerable when rooted mainly in temporary or project-based impulses and not yet fully embedded in institutional or national structures.

Consideration:

Long-term sustainability is strengthened when funding mechanisms, institutional strategies, and collaborative arrangements are designed with multi-year continuity and structural anchoring in mind. Shared responsibility among institutions, infrastructure organisations, and national bodies can help ensure that community networks, expertise, and open-science infrastructures persist beyond individual project cycles.

Advice:

- Commit to long-term support of Open Science to make it sustainable and affirm long-term commitment with structural support
- Help secure long-term funding and clear mandates for the Digital Competence Centres, ensuring that technical expertise, domain alignment, and interoperability can grow beyond short project cycles.
- Embed Open Science in institutional strategies, departmental plans, and leadership expectations.
- Provide researchers and support staff with protected time for data management, software work, community building, and societal engagement.
- Reduce fragmentation by adopting interoperable and sustainable infrastructures, including Digital Competence Centres.
- Safeguard OSNL's accumulated social capital and momentum.

A second observation on sustainability:

While in-kind contributions from universities was mentioned by several applicants as an option to promote sustainability of initiatives after the impulse funding from OSNL, in-kind contribution requirements that approach parity with requested support can deter smaller actors, including universities of applied sciences, thereby narrowing consortium diversity.

Consideration:

Calibrating co-funding expectations to the capacities of different institution types would support equitable participation without weakening commitments.

Advice:

Reconsider co-funding requirements taking in-kind funding and institutional capacity into account

Observation on geopolitical and technological pressures:

Interviewees expressed concern that broader geopolitical and technological developments may challenge Open Science principles. Questions around responsible AI, digital autonomy, and knowledge security were regarded as increasingly influential for the conditions under which openness can be sustained. Stakeholders asked for a structured approach to AI and knowledge security rather than ad-hoc responses.

Consideration:

The 2026–2027 programme’s AI & Open Science mapping exercise and the national coordination track for access to sensitive data offer anchors for a broader “responsible AI in Open Science” framework. A coherent approach to emerging challenges benefits from cross-actor dialogue and clarity around the roles of various stakeholders, including ministries, infrastructure providers, and institutions. Roadmaps or shared frameworks that integrate Open Science principles with evolving concerns around AI and security can help ensure that openness remains viable and valued amid shifting external pressures.

Advice:

- Continue leading professional communication and prioritise convening as a form of ‘people infrastructure’ that sustains collaboration.
- Explore synergies between Open Science and knowledge security to position openness as a strategic asset.
- Make research systems more resilient by supporting transparent practices and shared standards. These help reveal risks earlier and support coordinated responses.

4.4 Coherence of OSNL initiatives

Coherence matters both conceptually and operationally: alignment with international principles, complementarity with national actors, and internal consistency across instruments. OSNL’s programmes are conceptually well-aligned with UNESCO/EOSC internationally and with NPOS 2030, SURF’s infrastructure strategy, and NWO’s TDCCs nationally. Internally, the portfolio links capacity building, infrastructure, robust research processes, evidence, and community empowerment rather than treating them as silos.

Observation on the funding landscape:

Perceived overlap in parts of infrastructure funding between OSNL and domain-oriented TDCC activities can create applicant confusion. In discussions with applicants, it was sometimes unclear whether they referred to OSNL funding or domain-specific TDCC calls, and on several occasions they mentioned that there was overlap and sometimes confusion between these calls. This confusion was also acknowledged by other interviewees, showing that OSNL is aware of this overlap and looking for a solution.

“Overlap is most visible in digital infrastructure funding between OSNL and TDCCs. While not harmful per se, it creates confusion for applicants. A more formal mapping of responsibilities could prevent duplication.”

Covenant Partners

Consideration:

A public role-mapping that clarifies scopes, hand-offs, and funding boundaries across actors would reduce duplication and transaction costs.

Advice:

- Clarify and communicate the programme’s nature and expectations consistently across constituencies.
- Reduce fragmentation by adopting interoperable and sustainable infrastructures, including Digital Competence Centres.
- Embed Open Science principles in all calls
- Align open-science requirements across programmes to ensure clarity and predictability.

Observation on equity:

Internationally, OSNL engages actively in European fora and is frequently described, in the covenant partners session, as a “trailblazer” for policy implementation. We note this as a stakeholder quote rather than a committee judgement. Interviewees mentioned that engagement beyond Europe, particularly with low- and middle-income countries, is less systematic.

“The programme aligns well with EOSC and UNESCO principles. The Netherlands is seen as a trailblazer in Europe... However, global engagement beyond Europe is weaker and needs more systematic effort.”

Covenant Partners

Consideration:

Embedding equity aims in future international actions would broaden relevance and mutual learning while it is for the Steering Board to assess the priority of international engagement as against Dutch engagement.

Advice:

Consider reviewing the international relationship of the OSNL programme, particularly with the lens of equity and inclusion.

Observation on matchmaking:

Applicants also valued call-level matchmaking after information sessions and at CS-NL events, which helps coherent consortia coalesce around shared needs.

Consideration:

Institutionalising such coordination mechanisms, through joint calls or shared evaluation frameworks, and ensuring other NWO calls embed open-science principles systematically would further strengthen coherence.

Advice:

- Embed Open Science principles in all calls
- Innovate on funding mechanisms to promote collaborations, including with non-academic partners
- Align open-science requirements across programmes to ensure clarity and predictability.

4.5 Efficiency

Efficiency, in this context, is the proportionate use of financial, human, and organisational resources to achieve intended goals, with lean design to minimise overhead while maintaining agility and transparency.

Observation on service orientation:

From the interviews, it was clear that the OSNL team and programme were highly efficient, and that the expertise they provided was above and beyond regular funding programmes.

“One thing that I really want to mention is that I'm very impressed [about how the team] works [...] If you see what they have, how they've managed to really put the money into the field is something that I really wanted to stress, which is important. They've done it very effectively. [...] I mean it's quite a job for them to manage these enormous amounts of applications. [...] I think they're actually doing more than you can expect.”

Covenant partners

Applicants also praised the team for being highly responsive and helpful. They described a number of examples where the OSNL team provided direct, rapid, and efficient support, and they described the team as “very reachable”, “very friendly”, and “service-minded”. The personal contact that the OSNL team established with applicants was highly valued.

Observation on overhead:

OSNL's 6% overhead cap and operational embedding within NWO are widely perceived by funders and many stakeholders as effective mechanisms for directing resources to the community, enabling rapid deployment of instruments and a disciplined coordination role.

However, perceptions of efficiency differ: governance bodies read low overhead as success, whereas applicants, particularly smaller institutions and early-career researchers, experience efficiency as clarity and accessibility.

Observation on programme capacity:

Efficiency entails trade-offs. The lean model creates structural vulnerabilities, limited staff capacity for the depth of engagement desired by both OSNL and stakeholders; reliance on NWO's procedural systems; and constrained flexibility to address emerging priorities. Programme leaders reported time spent on administration that could otherwise be devoted to strategic engagement and innovation. This is especially important considering that OSNL programme leaders were selected among the leading Open Science experts in the country. Interviewees mentioned that programme leaders' involvement in OSNL was a great advantage to the programme, but that the time and efforts they needed to spend on administrative roles came at a cost by removing their time and involvement from the Open Science community. Worries about the demands and risk of burnout were voiced by several interviewees.

“The team is extremely well equipped [...] to work with the community to translate developments and requests from the community to the financial instruments that Open Science is holding. [...] I think you could make more of it if there's somebody [who] takes the burden away of running European tender processes. [...] The programme managers are doing that which is such a shame, and such a waste of energy and talent, I think, indeed. Then on paper it looks less efficient if we spend more than 6% on the team and all that. But I think in practice it will be much more efficient.”

Steering board

Consideration:

Modest reinvestment in human resources and digital tooling would reduce burnout risks and increase strategic bandwidth without sacrificing cost-consciousness. Some interviewees mentioned that for instance the National Science Agenda (NSA) allows for more than 6% overhead cap.

Advice:

- Provide more in-kind support for managing calls so the OSNL team can focus on engagement and coordination.
- Revisit overhead levels and administrative constraints, including salary-scale rigidity, and learn from OSNL's experience to refine funding instruments that enable mixed teams and community building.

Observation on transaction costs:

Complex tendering processes and competitive calls, though transparent, impose high transaction costs and can exclude less-resourced actors.

Consideration:

Streamlining application steps and harmonising requirements where feasible would preserve rigour while improving access.

Advice:

- Clarify the different roles, responsibilities, and funding pathways of the various stakeholders in the Dutch Open Science landscape.
- Reconsider co-funding requirements taking in-kind funding and institutional capacity into account

- Revisit overhead levels and administrative constraints, including salary-scale rigidity, and learn from OSNL's experience to refine funding instruments that enable mixed teams and community building.

Observation on funding rules:

Further observations touch on equity and clarity. Rigidity embedded in funding calls may disadvantage community liaisons and non-academic experts relative to researchers, weakening distributed expertise central to citizen science.

Consideration:

Closer alignment between call text, briefings, and panel rubrics, and lighter-weight procedures for small grants, would improve efficiency across the portfolio.

In response, stakeholders suggested a practical set of actions: introduce administrative or in-kind support and digital tools to relieve programme leaders; develop mechanisms that respond quickly to emerging priorities (AI, knowledge security) without over-burdening compliance; and monitor equity so that process efficiencies do not amplify disparities among institution types. For NWO as hosting organisation, provide additional operational support for call management and administrative support; review salary-scale and the use of procurements to support non-academic expertise and community partners; and co-design lighter procedures for small grants and tenders aimed at new entrants and smaller actors.

Advice:

- Revisit overhead levels and administrative constraints, including salary-scale rigidity, and learn from OSNL's experience to refine funding instruments that enable mixed teams and community building.
- Coordinate national visions while supporting bottom-up work. Partners should help shape national roadmaps for infrastructure, skills, and community engagement. At the same time, they should preserve the bottom-up energy that has driven much of OSNL's success.

4.6 Effectiveness

Effectiveness is judged through early outcomes, outputs delivered, engagement created, and signs of cultural change. Within two years, OSNL delivered a broad portfolio of calls and initiatives, including recognition-and-rewards instruments and community events such as Open Science Meetings and the annual festival.

Observation on indications of cultural change:

Interviewees pointed to early signals of cultural change, notably increased collaboration across institutions and disciplines and greater visibility for open practices.

Awareness and engagement have risen, supported by inclusive events and low-threshold instruments that enable participation by early-career researchers and support staff. Yet, interviewees noted that a lack of visibility of the achievements of funded projects may jeopardise institutional buy-in.

Visibility, visibility, visibility. Make it visible where it was successful.

Funded applicants

"Maybe jump in and try to figure out, get the best use cases, get it published, get it... get it visible. Yeah. Let people show how good it is. And I think that is what is needed, but that we have a platform where we just promote. [...] What the results are. Yeah. And what the positive effects are on Open Science."

Funded applicants

Considerations:

Publishing compelling use cases that demonstrate interoperability and tangible benefits would help make impacts and benefits of Open Science visible and transferable, contributing to institution buy-in and sustainability. Long-term embedding of Open Science and sustainability depend on institutional commitments and stable funding beyond programme timeframes.

Advice

- Support showcasing effectiveness of the OSNL programme, for example through success stories
- Amplify OSNL's goals. Partners act as a bridge between national ambitions and local practice. Clear and coordinated communication will strengthen engagement and understanding across their communities.
- Recognise open practices to support cultural change.

Observation on converging roles:

Several interviewees stressed the exceptional value of bringing together all relevant partners who play a role in OSNL's coordination and expressed great value in being able to discuss and move together. Interviewees even noted that convergence seemed to be moving partners towards a momentum. However, a lack of clarity in the specific roles and responsibilities each partner has towards OSNL's mandate still seemed to create confusion and to slow action.

“The Bestuurlijk Overleg [covenant partners] deals with all the people who are actually steering in their specific organisations. So we cannot make the decisions here, but at least we can coordinate all activities that we're driving in the right direction and exchange that in an open way where we can have that discussion. So this coordinating effort is important because in the end, if we want to have a European approach to Open Science as well, which OSNL tries to bring forward, there has to be a form, a shape or form where you can make a kind of a national plan and a national strategy. [...] We feel that we are converging, we feel that we're having momentum.”

Covenant Partners

Consideration:

Covenant partners should engage positively and confidently with OSNL, recognising its role not as a constraint but as a shared strategic asset — one that elevates the capacity of the entire system rather than diminishing institutional autonomy.

Advice

- Clarify the different roles, responsibilities, and funding pathways of the various stakeholders in the Dutch Open Science landscape.
- Work together to identify the necessary compromises across partners to strengthen implementation and coherence. As far as possible, partners should align incentives, procedures, and expectations, and provide staff with clear guidance for open workflows.
- Clarify responsibilities among Covenant Partners, for recognition-and-rewards, infrastructure stewardship, and skills pipelines to reduce friction between local expectations and national instruments and support continued effectiveness.

4.7 Sustainability

Sustainability refers to the resilience and long-term embedding of Open Science practices after impulse funding ends: financial continuity, cultural normalisation, infrastructure robustness, and equity across institution types. OSNL has catalysed momentum through funding, community building, and infrastructure pilots; sustaining and scaling these achievements beyond the decade is the principal challenge.

Observation on financial sustainability:

Interviewees repeatedly mentioned that financial fragility follows from budget cuts and reliance on temporary grants. Institutional inertia risks uneven adoption, with some universities embedding Open Science in strategy while others lag.

“The biggest risk facing this programme is this embedding pathway and is ensuring that there's capacity and really it has to be in the fundamental revenue streams. It shouldn't be constantly having to fight for funding because then you leave a whole collaborative community hanging.”

Advisory Panel

Consideration on institutional commitment:

Financial sustainability cannot be realised without a collaborative effort between stakeholders involved. The evaluation committee welcomed the Covenant Partners' enthusiasm to secure institutional commitments and co-funding models.

Advice:

- Commit to long-term support of Open Science to make it sustainable and affirm long-term commitment with structural support.
- Help secure long-term funding and clear mandates for the Digital Competence Centres, ensuring that technical expertise, domain alignment, and interoperability can grow beyond short project cycles.

Observation on institutional capacity:

Interviewees stressed that requiring projects to include realistic long-term plans and institutional fund-matching is necessary to sustain investments beyond impulse funding. However, some interviewees also worried that requirements for fund-matching may deter small institutions from participating.

Consideration:

Where appropriate, grant conditionality that requires institutions to formalise funding streams and collaborations post-award have proven to be key instruments, but also considering institutional capabilities to avoid inequities towards small institutions and universities of applied sciences is important.

Advice:

- Commit to long-term support of Open Science to make it sustainable and affirm long-term commitment with structural support
- Reconsider co-funding requirements taking in-kind funding and institutional capacity into account

Observation on embedding sustainability:

Interviewees stressed that human sustainability matters as much as technology and funding sustainability. “Warm bodies” are needed to maintain community practices, tools, and liaison roles beyond project cycles.

Consideration:

Sustainable Open Science depends on staff such as data stewards, software specialists, librarians, and community managers. Institutions should treat these roles as essential infrastructure, not as temporary additions. Balancing technological investments with investments in people, skills, support, and staff continuity is important for sustainable community building. Providing protected time for Open Science and opportunities for skills building is key to providing sustainability in the people behind Open Science.

Advice:

- Provide protected time for staff, secure funding for coordination roles, and integrate Open Science into strategies and governance. Embedding Open Science requires consistent and practical choices and goes well beyond policy statements.

- Provide researchers and support staff with protected time for data management, software work, community building, and societal engagement.
- Provide training to support responsible open research practices (e.g., ethics, integrity, privacy, data stewardship).

Observation on recognition:

Interviewees – in particular applicants and early career researchers – stressed the lack of recognition that currently exists for Open Science in research careers. Early career researchers explained that Open Science skills and practices highly depend on early career researchers' buy-in, yet they have little impact on career advancement and the time and skills needed for these practices can push back and delay other practices which are currently counted towards advancing their career. They also stressed the importance of harmonising recognition and rewards at least on a national level and working systematically with science education from high school levels to enable “*broad cultural work*” that reshape the perspectives of a good researcher.

“Entering the academic job market based on Open Science alone is, from what I hear, really difficult.”

“The implementation of recognition and rewards already differs between faculties at one university, let alone between universities, so harmonisation would be amazing.”

Early career researchers

Consideration:

Recognition for open research practices and skills is crucial to ensure a genuine culture change and to fulfil OSNL's objective of making Open Science the norm. Cultural embedding of Open Science depends on coherent recognition-and-rewards reform so that open practices are normal rather than peripheral. University leadership, funders, and other stakeholders must work together towards a shared recognition of open research practices.

Advice:

- Support showcasing effectiveness of the OSNL programme, for example through success stories
- Recognition-and-rewards policies should value open practices consistently across faculties and, where possible, be harmonised between institutions.
- Advocate for recognition of open practices within your institutions and contribute to shaping fair assessment systems.
- Recognise open practices to support cultural change.

Observation on knowledge security:

Interviewees raised concern about the increasingly unstable political and financial landscapes and with the growing influence that these instabilities have on research systems. Funding insecurities and tensions in investment, for example between Open Science and research security, or between bottom up initiatives and the growing dependence on big commercial technologies, were mentioned as concerns for the future of Open Science.

Consideration:

The evaluation committee perceives that Open Science should not be seen in opposition to knowledge security, but as an ally to support and enable adequate security. Making failures visible and providing a structured framework for safe information management and sharing, openness can inform and improve both domains. This positions OSNL as a thought leader for responsible openness, not by balancing openness against security, but by demonstrating how openness can enhance it. Equally, continuing to value and embrace bottom-up initiatives and input is crucial to preserve capacity and independence that is essential for making Open Science sustainable.

Advice:

- Amplify OSNL's goals. Partners act as a bridge between national ambitions and local practice. Clear and coordinated communication will strengthen engagement and understanding across their communities.
- Coordinate national visions while supporting bottom-up work. Partners should help shape national roadmaps for infrastructure, skills, and community engagement. At the same time, they should preserve the bottom-up energy that has driven much of OSNL's success.
- Explore synergies between Open Science and knowledge security to position openness as a strategic asset.
- Make research systems more resilient by supporting transparent practices and shared standards. These help reveal risks earlier and support coordinated responses.

5 Recommendations

5.1 Evaluation synthesis

Achievements and coherence

The evaluation of OSNL during its formative years reveals a programme that has moved decisively from aspiration to implementation, catalysing systemic change across the Dutch research landscape. In less than three years, OSNL has established a coherent portfolio that spans infrastructure, capacity building, incentives, and community empowerment. This breadth and pace of delivery are exceptional by any international standard and have positioned the Netherlands as a frontrunner in operationalising Open Science principles.

Strengths and strategic design

Stakeholders consistently acknowledged OSNL's catalytic role in translating national ambitions into practical instruments. The programme's design reflects a systemic reading of the transition: skills, infrastructure, and incentives are addressed together rather than in isolation. This integrated approach has created mutually reinforcing levers of change, ensuring that progress in one area enables progress in others. The evaluation committee commends OSNL for this strategic coherence and for maintaining momentum despite fiscal constraints.

Challenges

At the same time, the evaluation surfaced challenges that warrant attention. Smaller institutions and universities of applied sciences expressed a need for deeper inclusion, particularly in shaping priorities and accessing funding instruments. Civil-society organisations, vital for citizen science, face practical barriers in meeting administrative requirements. Addressing these issues will strengthen OSNL's relevance and equity without compromising accountability. Emerging themes such as responsible AI and knowledge security also require a structured response to maintain coherence and mission clarity.

Efficiency

Efficiency has been a hallmark of OSNL's operations. A lean programme office, operating within a 6% overhead cap and leveraging NWO's established processes, has enabled rapid deployment of instruments. Yet this efficiency entails trade-offs: limited staff capacity constrains the depth of engagement desired by both OSNL and stakeholders. Modest reinvestment in human resources and digital tooling would help reduce burnout risks. It would also expand strategic bandwidth. Focusing this reinvestment on substantive coordination rather than administrative tasks avoids pressure on the 6% overhead cap. Because substantive coordination directly supports programme delivery, improving capacity in this area does not conflict with cost-consciousness. Similarly, streamlining application steps and harmonising requirements for smaller grants would preserve rigour while improving access for less-resourced actors.

Effectiveness and sustainability

Effectiveness is visible in early outcomes: approximately 218 projects funded by end-2025, strong engagement through the Open Science Festival and community meetings, and rising enthusiasm across institutions. These signals of cultural change, greater collaboration, increased visibility for open practices, are encouraging. Sustainability, however, remains the principal challenge. Impulse funding has generated momentum, but long-term embedding depends on structural integration within institutional strategies, stable resourcing, and coherent recognition-and-rewards reform. Governance clarity for roles such as DCC stewardship and software maintenance will be critical to avoid fragmentation.

5.2 Overview of recommendations and advice

Against this backdrop, the committee offers forward-looking recommendations, and specific advice grouped by stakeholder to provide clarity and shared responsibility.

Key recommendations

1. Actively implement the new work programme, maintaining its coherent design and momentum: stay the course.
2. Strengthen capacity within the OSNL team to engage further with the community.
3. Clarify roles and responsibilities of the different stakeholders in the Open Science system.
4. Promote sustainability beyond impulse funding. Deliver an infrastructure vision.
5. Continue to create a research culture that enables and encourages the research community to engage in Open Science

5.2.1 Advice for OSNL programme

To the OSNL programme Team

RECOMMENDATION 1. Actively implement the new work programme, maintaining its coherent design and momentum: stay the course.

- 1.1 Continue leading professional communication and prioritise convening as a form of ‘people infrastructure’ that sustains collaboration.
- 1.2 Safeguard OSNL’s accumulated social capital and momentum.
- 1.3 Allow justified flexibility to funding eligibility rules where needed.

RECOMMENDATION 3. Clarify roles and responsibilities of the different stakeholders in the Open Science system

- 3.1 Increase clarity in future calls on the success criteria
- 3.2 Clarify the different roles, responsibilities, and funding pathways of the various stakeholders in the Dutch Open Science landscape.

RECOMMENDATION 5. Continue to create a research culture that enables and encourages the research community to engage in Open Science

- 5.1 Support showcasing effectiveness of the OSNL programme, for example through success stories

To the Steering Board

RECOMMENDATION 1. Actively implement the new work programme, maintaining its coherent design and momentum: stay the course.

- 1.1 Continue to be hands-on in mobilising sectors and championing programme needs.
- 1.2 Consider reviewing the international relationship of the OSNL programme, particularly with the lens of equity and inclusion.

RECOMMENDATION 3. Clarify roles and responsibilities of the different stakeholders in the Open Science system

- 3.1 Clarify and communicate the programme’s nature and expectations consistently across constituencies.

To the Covenant Partners

RECOMMENDATION 1. Actively implement the new work programme, maintaining its coherent design and momentum: stay the course.

- 1.1 Work together to identify the necessary compromises across partners to strengthen implementation and coherence. As far as possible, partners should align incentives, procedures, and expectations, and provide staff with clear guidance for open workflows.

1.2 Amplify OSNL's goals. Partners act as a bridge between national ambitions and local practice. Clear and coordinated communication will strengthen engagement and understanding across their communities.

RECOMMENDATION 3. Clarify roles and responsibilities of the different stakeholders in the Open Science system

3.1 Clarify responsibilities among Covenant Partners, for recognition-and-rewards, infrastructure stewardship, and skills pipelines to reduce friction between local expectations and national instruments and support continued effectiveness.

RECOMMENDATION 4. Promote sustainability beyond impulse funding. Deliver an infrastructure vision.

4.1 Commit to long-term support of Open Science to make it sustainable and affirm long-term commitment with structural support.

4.2 Coordinate national visions while supporting bottom-up work. Partners should help shape national roadmaps for infrastructure, skills, and community engagement. At the same time, they should preserve the bottom-up energy that has driven much of OSNL's success.

4.3 Help secure long-term funding and clear mandates for the Digital Competence Centres, ensuring that technical expertise, domain alignment, and interoperability can grow beyond short project cycles.

RECOMMENDATION 5. Continue to create a research culture that enables and encourages the research community to engage in Open Science

5.1 Provide protected time for staff, secure funding for coordination roles, and integrate Open Science into strategies and governance. Embedding Open Science requires consistent and practical choices and goes well beyond policy statements.

To NWO

RECOMMENDATION 1. Actively implement the new work programme, maintaining its coherent design and momentum: stay the course.

1.1 Reconsider co-funding requirements taking in-kind funding and institutional capacity into account.

RECOMMENDATION 2. Strengthen capacity within the OSNL team to engage further with the community

2.1 Provide more in-kind support for managing calls so the OSNL team can focus on engagement and coordination.

2.2 Revisit overhead levels and administrative constraints, including salary-scale rigidity, and learn from OSNL's experience to refine funding instruments that enable mixed teams and community building.

RECOMMENDATION 3. Clarify roles and responsibilities of the different stakeholders in the Open Science system

3.1 Rules and regulations (legislative) as well as NWO policies encourage broader participation in the OSNL programme.

5.2.2 Advice for Universities and Other Knowledge Institutions

RECOMMENDATION 1. Actively implement the new work programme, maintaining its coherent design and momentum: stay the course.

1.1 Contribute to practice-oriented research and have close relationships with societal partners. Stakeholders highlighted both their strong engagement and the barriers they face.

1.2 Work with OSNL and NWO to ensure fair access to funding schemes and to reduce administrative burdens.

RECOMMENDATION 3. Clarify roles and responsibilities of the different stakeholders in the Open Science system

3.1 Reduce fragmentation by adopting interoperable and sustainable infrastructures, including Digital Competence Centres.

3.2 Help harmonise policies for responsible data access and sharing. Their expertise positions them to guide national standards for secure, FAIR data infrastructures.

RECOMMENDATION 4. Promote sustainability beyond impulse funding. Deliver an infrastructure vision.

4.1 Commit to long-term support of Open Science to make it sustainable and affirm long-term commitment with structural support.

RECOMMENDATION 5. Continue to create a research culture that enables and encourages the research community to engage in Open Science

5.1 Embed Open Science in institutional strategies, departmental plans, and leadership expectations.

5.2 Value Open Science and open practices in recognition-and-rewards policies consistently across faculties and, where possible, harmonise recognition-and-rewards policies between institutions.

5.3 Provide researchers and support staff with protected time for data management, software work, community building, and societal engagement.

5.3 Provide training to support responsible open research practices (e.g., ethics, integrity, privacy, data stewardship).

5.2.3 Advice for Researchers and Research Staff

RECOMMENDATION 1. Actively implement the new work programme, maintaining its coherent design and momentum: stay the course.

1.1 Embrace the opportunities OSNL creates for shaping the future of research. Your involvement is essential to embed openness as a norm for the next generation.

RECOMMENDATION 5. Continue to create a research culture that enables and encourages the research community to engage in Open Science

5.1 Engage actively in Open Science Communities and citizen-science initiatives to build networks and skills.

5.2 Advocate for recognition of open practices within your institutions and contribute to shaping fair assessment systems.

5.3 Continue to champion Open Science practices, including FAIR principles.

5.2.4 Advice for Libraries and Library Consortia

RECOMMENDATION 4. Promote sustainability beyond impulse funding. Deliver an infrastructure vision.

4.1 Continue to support sustainable, non-profit publishing models, including diamond open access with support from universities and other knowledge institutions. Libraries are essential to knowledge stewardship and open-access publishing.

4.2 Advance metadata standards, persistent identifiers, and interoperability across institutions.

RECOMMENDATION 5. Continue to create a research culture that enables and encourages the research community to engage in Open Science

5.1 Strengthen Open Science literacy by offering training on topics such as data sharing and open peer review.

5.2 Host Open Science Communities and support bottom-up activity.

5.2.5 Advice for Research Funders

RECOMMENDATION 1. Actively implement the new work programme, maintaining its coherent design and momentum: stay the course.

1.1 Embed Open Science principles in all calls

1.2 Innovate on funding mechanisms to promote collaborations, including with non-academic partners.

RECOMMENDATION 3. Clarify roles and responsibilities of the different stakeholders in the Open Science system

3.1 Align open-science requirements across programmes to ensure clarity and predictability.

RECOMMENDATION 5. Continue to create a research culture that enables and encourages the research community to engage in Open Science

5.1 Recognise open practices to support cultural change.

5.2.6 Advice for Ministries and Parliament

RECOMMENDATION 4. Promote sustainability beyond impulse funding. Deliver an infrastructure vision.

4.1 Rebuild and retain Open Science policy expertise within the ministries, expanding its scope to include Open Education.

4.2 Explore synergies between Open Science and knowledge security to position openness as a strategic asset.

4.3 Make research systems more resilient by supporting transparent practices and shared standards. These help reveal risks earlier and support coordinated responses.

Glossary

AI (Artificial Intelligence):

Technologies and methods that enable machines to perform tasks that typically require human intelligence, such as learning, reasoning, and problem-solving. In the context of Open Science, AI raises questions about responsible use and knowledge security.

CARE Principles

Guidelines for the governance of Indigenous data: *Collective Benefit, Authority to Control, Responsibility, and Ethics*. Complements FAIR principles by emphasizing equity and ethics.

Citizen Science

Research conducted in collaboration with members of the public, who contribute data, knowledge, or expertise. OSNL supports this through Citizen Science Hubs and the CS-NL network.

CoARA (Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment)

An international initiative promoting reform of research assessment to recognize diverse contributions, including Open Science practices.

CoNOSC (Council of National Open Science Coordinators)

A global network of national-level Open Science coordinators sharing strategies and good practices.

Diamond Open Access

A publishing model where scholarly works are freely accessible to readers and authors without fees, typically funded by institutions or consortia.

DCC (Digital Competence Centre)

Institutional or domain-specific hubs providing expertise and support for research data management and FAIR practices. Includes LDCCs (Local DCCs) and TDCCs (Thematic DCCs).

EOSC (European Open Science Cloud)

A European initiative to create a federated environment for sharing research data and services across borders and disciplines.

FAIR Principles

Standards for data and research outputs: *Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable*. Widely adopted in Open Science to ensure data quality and usability.

GA4GH Passports / DUO

Standards for secure and ethical access to sensitive data, developed by the Global Alliance for Genomics and Health.

NPOS 2030 (National Plan Open Science 2030)

The Dutch national strategy for embedding Open Science practices across research by 2030.

NWO (Nederlandse Organisatie voor Wetenschappelijk Onderzoek)

The Dutch Research Council, responsible for funding research and hosting OSNL.

OAI-ORE (Open Archives Initiative Object Reuse and Exchange)

OAI-ORE defines standards for describing and exchanging aggregations of web resources—also known as compound digital objects.

[ODRL \(Open Digital Rights Language\)](#)

A standard for expressing permissions and restrictions for digital content, relevant for managing sensitive data.

[Open Science](#)

An inclusive approach to research that makes scientific knowledge openly available, accessible, and reusable; fosters collaboration; and engages societal actors in knowledge creation.

[OSC-NL \(Open Science Communities Netherlands\)](#)

A national network of local Open Science Communities that promote grassroots engagement and knowledge sharing.

[POSI \(Principles of Open Scholarly Infrastructure\)](#)

Guidelines for building sustainable, community-governed scholarly infrastructure.

[RDA \(Research Data Alliance\)](#)

The Research Data Alliance is a global, community-driven initiative, aiming to build the social and technical bridges that enable open sharing and reuse of research data across disciplines, technologies, and countries.

[Recognition and Rewards](#)

Policy reforms aimed at valuing diverse contributions in research careers, including Open Science practices, teaching, and societal engagement.

[ReSA \(Research Software Alliance\)](#)

ReSA is an international initiative dedicated to strengthening the research software ecosystem.

[UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science](#)

A global framework adopted in 2021 that defines principles, values, and actions for implementing Open Science worldwide.

List of references

- Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment. (2022). Agreement on reforming research assessment. <https://coara.eu/agreement/>
- Council of the European Union. (2016). Council conclusions on the transition towards an Open Science system.
- CWTS & Dialogic. (in progress). Monitoring framework and dashboard prototype for OSNL. Commissioned by Open Science NL.
- European Commission. (2019). European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) strategic implementation plan. <https://doi.org/10.2777/202370>
- European Open Science Cloud Association. (2024). Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA v1.3). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17582648>
- Global Indigenous Data Alliance. (2019). CARE Principles for Indigenous Data Governance. <https://doi.org/10.5334/dsj-2020-043>
- Invest in Open Infrastructure. (2023). Principles of Open Scholarly Infrastructure (POSI). <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.b16f42>
- Leonelli, S. (2023). Philosophy of Open Science. Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/9781009416368>
- Ministerie van Onderwijs, Cultuur en Wetenschap. (2015). De waarde(n) van weten: Strategische agenda hoger onderwijs en onderzoek 2015–2025. <https://www.rijksfinancien.nl/sites/default/files/extrainfo/ocw/strategische-agenda-hoger-onderwijs.pdf>
- Ministerie van Onderwijs, Cultuur en Wetenschap. (2023). Convenant Regieorgaan Open Science. <https://www.rijksoverheid.nl/documenten/convenanten/2023/03/15/bijlage-convenant-regieorgaan-open-science>
- Ministerie van Onderwijs en Wetenschappen. (1974). Nota wetenschapsbeleid 1974.
- National Plan Open Science (2017) I 2017–2020. National Plan Open Science. <https://doi.org/10.4233/uuid:9e9fa82e-06c1-4d0d-9e20-5620259a6c65>
- National Plan Open Science (2022) II. (2021–2024). Open Science 2030 in the Netherlands. NPOS2030 Ambition Document and Rolling Agenda – Version 1. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7433767>
- Nationale Wetenschapsagenda. (2015). Nationale Wetenschapsagenda voor Nederland. <https://archive.org/details/blg-631503>
- Nosek, B. A. (2019). Strategy for culture change. Center for Open Science. <https://www.cos.io/blog/strategy-for-culture-change>
- OECD. (2004). Declaration on access to research data from public funding. <https://legalinstruments.oecd.org/public/doc/157/157.en.pdf>
- OECD. (2006). Recommendation of the Council concerning access to research data from public funding. <https://legalinstruments.oecd.org/api/print?ids=159&lang=en>
- Open Science NL. (2023). Open Science NL Work programme 2024–2025. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10074873>
- Open Science NL. (2025). Open Science NL Work programme 2026–2027. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17579088>
- Open Science NL. (2025). Self-reflection Open Science NL 2023–2025. UNESCO. (2021). Recommendation on Open Science. <https://doi.org/10.54677/XOIR1696>
- VSNU, NFWO, KNAW, NWO, & ZonMw. (2019). Ruimte voor ieders talent. <https://www.universiteitenvannederland.nl/files/publications/Position%20paper%20Ruimte%20voor%20ieders%20talent.pdf>
- Wilkinson, M. D., Dumontier, M., Aalbersberg, I. J., Appleton, G., Axton, M., Baak, A., ... Mons, B. (2016). The FAIR guiding principles for scientific data management and stewardship. *Scientific Data*, 3, Article 160018. <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>

Annex 1: Terms of Reference for the evaluation of Open Science NL

1. Reason for and object of the evaluation

Reason

The Covenant Regieorgaan Open Science states in Article 8 that "NWO will ensure that the functioning of the Regieorgaan is evaluated in 2025, in 2029 and in 2031 (final evaluation)."

Subject of the evaluation

The subject of the evaluation is the Regieorgaan Open Science NL, hereafter referred to as Open Science NL. This includes the functioning of the Steering Committee, the Director and the staff of Open Science NL. Open Science NL was established as a temporary unit within NWO on March 29, 2023. Its activities are guided by a Covenant signed on March 29, 2023 by 16 parties, including the Ministry of OCW.¹

2. Aim and purpose of the evaluation

Aim

The evaluation will cover the first 2 years of Open Science NL. This period should be characterized as a start-up phase. The work during these initial years was guided by a work programme, resulting in the development of a first set of funding instruments and the awarding of initial projects. However, as most projects are still in the implementation phase, it is not yet possible to fully assess their impact. This first evaluation should therefore focus on four evaluation criteria appropriate for the organization's first two years: relevance, coherence, efficiency, and the early indicators of effectiveness.

¹ NWO (Netherlands Organisation for Scientific Research); ZonMw (Netherlands Organisation for Health Research and Development); VSNU (Association of Universities in the Netherlands); KNAW (Royal Netherlands Academy of Arts and Sciences); SURF (Collaborative organization for ICT in Dutch education and research); NFU (Netherlands Federation of University Medical Centers); VH (Association of Universities of Applied Sciences); DANS (Data Archiving and Networked Services) Rathenau Institute; PBL (Netherlands Environmental Assessment Agency); CBS (Statistics Netherlands); NWO-I (NWO Institutes Organisation); NWO-SGW (NWO Social Sciences and Humanities); NWO-ENW (NWO Science Domain); NWO-ZonMw (NWO Health Research and Development); NWO-TTW (NWO Applied and Engineering Sciences)

Intended use

The main purpose of the evaluation is to gain insight into the functioning of Open Science NL during the evaluation period, primarily for NWO and OCW as the main funders, but also for Open Science NL itself, its Steering Board, and the other covenant parties who could benefit from the recommendations of the evaluation committee. The covenant states: "Formal consultations will take place with the parties and OCW as commissioner [of the Open Science NL programme] on the follow-up to the results of the evaluation. Parties will enter into further arrangements in this regard." The evaluation will result in a concise report, which will be made publicly available on the websites of NWO and Open Science NL, and will be presented by OCW to the Dutch Parliament.

3. Scope of the evaluation: stakeholders and time period

Period

The evaluation covers 26 months: from the start date of Open Science NL, 29 March 2023, to 1 June 2025.

Parties involved

The forums and individuals involved in the evaluation are as follows:

- The NWO Executive Board as the commissioning body of this evaluation.
- The Steering Board, director and staff of Open Science NL as the objects of the evaluation
- An evaluation committee to be established by NWO including a secretary as the executor of the evaluation.
- Community members to be consulted by the evaluation committee.
- Covenant parties of Open Science NL.

After consultation with the covenant parties, the outcome of the evaluation will be presented to the Minister of OCW by the NWO Executive Board - supplemented with commentary from the Steering Board and the NWO Executive Board.

4. Evaluation questions

The four main questions for the evaluation of the Regieorgaan Open Science, based on the terms of reference outlined in the Covenant, are:

1. Relevance: To what extent has Open Science NL focused on the right priorities in its first two years, and to what extent do its activities match the needs of the field, and both the national and international developments in open science?
2. Coherence: To what extent is there coherence and alignment between the initiatives of Open Science NL and other relevant initiatives, both national and international?
3. Efficiency: To what extent has Open Science NL used the available resources efficiently in its first two years to achieve its intended goals?
4. Effectiveness: What initial outcomes can be identified?

5. Basis for assessment: what is the basis for evaluating the object?

The following materials will be provided to answer the evaluation questions:

- These terms of reference
- The Open Science NL covenant

- The work programme 2024-2025, which is the basis for the activities of Open Science NL for the first period.
- Relevant background information to be provided by Open Science NL, including relevant (inter)national policy developments, including the decision to reduce the Open Science NL budget, etc.

6. Workflow

- The evaluation will be carried out by an independent committee (consisting of 3 people, with both national and international members). This committee will be supported by an external independent secretary who will be responsible for organising the process and writing the evaluation report.
- The members of the committee will be appointed by the NWO Executive Board
- During the evaluation a two-day site visit will be organized during which the evaluation committee will interview at least the Steering Board and staff of Open Science NL, representatives of the covenant parties, representatives of projects funded by Open Science NL, and others the committee may deem necessary to interview in order to properly answer the evaluation questions.
- The committee secretary will organize the site visit in cooperation with the Open Science NL secretariat.
- The evaluation report will be written by the secretary in close consultation with the committee.

7. Methods

The evaluation will be carried out by the committee through a combination of desk research using documentation to be provided by Open Science NL and interviews to be conducted by the committee with key stakeholders in the programme (during the site visit). Beyond these requirements, the evaluation committee will determine its own preferred working methods.

8. Timing, schedule of implementation and budget

Timing

June 2025 – March 2026

Planning

The schedule outline is as follows:

Decision on the terms of reference (NWO)	Before summer 2025
Appointment of the evaluation committee (NWO)	Q3 2025
Appointment of secretary to the evaluation committee	Q3 2025
Site visit (2 or 3 days)	Q4 2025
Draft evaluation report presented to NWO	Jan 2026
Presentation of final evaluation report (including response by the NWO Executive Board) to OCW/covenant parties	March 2026

Budget

The costs of the evaluation will be budgeted by the NWO Executive Board office.

9. Use and publication rights

The evaluation report along with response by NWO will be presented to OCW and published on the NWO and Open Science NL websites. The report will be presented to the Dutch Parliament by OCW. Publication rights are assigned to the NWO Executive Board.

10. Consultation

During the preparation of these terms of reference, the following parties and individuals were consulted:

- Covenant parties Open Science NL (in writing).
- Suzanne Caarls, MT member OWB department, Ministry of OCW
- Dirk Verloop, MI&O team leader, OWB department, Ministry of OCW
- Hans de Jonge, director of Open Science NL
- Open Science NL Steering Board, dated: 15-1-2025
- Prof. Dr. Arfan Ikram, portfolio holder Open Science, NWO Executive Board
- Prof. Marcel Levi, portfolio holder for evaluations, NWO Executive Board

11. Documentation

Appendix 1

Annex 2: Interview guides

This annex includes, for illustrative purposes, one of the interview guides used by the Evaluation Committee during the site visit interviews. The guides were developed on the basis of a shared core structure, complemented by few interview-specific points of attention.

Advisory Panels (45 min)

Time: 26 November 2025 - 14:15 – 15:05

Lead:

Format: Semi-structured interviews, 50 min (followed by a combined semi-structured interview, 45 min)

Purpose: Building a better understanding towards evaluating the Open Science NL programme, specifically through the areas of Relevance, Coherence, Efficiency, Effectiveness, and Sustainability. Getting a clear view on the experiences of members of the advisory panels on the four programme lines.

Participant: Advisory Panel Members

Protocol:

INTRODUCTION (5 min)

Introduction to the evaluation project and the purpose of the interview, with an explanation of the five pillars upon which the evaluation will take place:

- **Relevance:** Did OSNL focus on the right priorities, and do these match the needs of the field and wider developments?
- **Coherence:** Is there coherence and alignment between the OSNL initiatives and other relevant initiatives, (inter)nationally?
- **Efficiency:** Has OSNL used the available resources efficiently to achieve its intended goals
- **Effectiveness:** What initial outcomes can be identified?
- **Sustainability:** Is OSNL future resilient in achieving impact on open science?

Explain that we will interview a broad array of stakeholders, and therefore, we may not tackle all pillars with them. **Explain that about 45 minutes in the interview, the Covenant Partners will join us and we will address questions that we think are relevant to both of them.**

Make clear that the evaluation takes place only two years after the beginning of the programme and therefore we do not expect all pillars to be completely fulfilled, and mention that the role of the evaluation should be seen as a way to identify areas of progress and make informed recommendations to surmount challenges, rather than to judge on the value of the programme as a whole.

CONSENT

Make sure participants understand the confidentiality or identifiability of their data and that they agree for us to use direct quotes which will be associated with their interview group (mentioning that they responded as Advisory Board Member).

Check that participant agrees to be recorded and agrees for the recording to be transcribed and summarised by selected AI software.

INTRODUCTIONS

Each interview panel member introduces themselves briefly and all participants mention who they are (name and affiliation/title only).

Objective	Guiding question
<p>10 Minutes</p> <p>Have a broad overview of the perspective from the interviewee regarding the programme achievements. This question is intentionally unguided to discover emerging themes which we may have missed by focusing on the 5 pillars.</p> <p>No guiding question.</p>	<p>In the first ten minutes, we would like you to discuss what you think are the key achievements that the OSNL programme has accomplished in the first two years of its establishment, and what are its greatest challenges for the future.</p>
Relevance	
BONUS (to target Citizen Science)	Possibly add a question directly to ask about the inclusion of citizen science as a core element of open science NL.
Coherence	
<p>10 Minutes</p> <p>Understand what links are made with international open science developments and how OSNL plans to continue to be involved in international discourse.</p> <p>Guiding question: To what extent are links made with international open science developments?</p>	<p>We see that the NPOS and OSNL documents reference UNESCO, EOSC, and other international frameworks.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Are there other recent examples where OSNL has actively participated in or shaped international open science initiatives — for example through joint calls, standards development, or contributions to EOSC task forces? – How can OSNL best monitor international open science developments and develop an effective strategy to influence these? <p>Possible prompts/follow-ups:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – <i>How does OSNL ensure that the projects it funds are compliant with or interoperable with international open science infrastructures (e.g. EOSC, FAIR data networks)?</i> – <i>As new global trends emerge (e.g. the intersection of AI and open science, new assessment regimes, data sovereignty), how does OSNL plan to adapt its orientation or engage internationally?</i> – <i>What mechanisms exist to ensure that Dutch open science monitoring aligns with international metrics and avoids redundant reporting burdens?</i>
Sustainability	
<p>10 Minutes</p> <p>Understand the perspective of the Advisory Panel with regards to future avenues and new technologies such as AI</p>	<p>New technologies such as AI are rapidly transforming research — many tools now generate drafts, code, suggest resources and literature. At the same time, geopolitical shifts have triggered an intense interest in the security of knowledge: its process, its products, and its institutions.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Do you think OSNL should position itself with regards to these transformations?

<p>Guiding question: How does OSNL see its role in relation to changes evolving from AI?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – How could OSNL ensure that its position respects and strengthens open-science principles (openness, reproducibility, auditability)? – Are there other emerging technologies OSNL should keep an eye and interest in? – How do you see the relationship between OS and knowledge security issues? Should we change course in OS? <p>Possible prompts/follow-ups:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – <i>Should OSNL develop or plan an explicit AI strategy or roadmap? If so, what are the key domains (training, infrastructure, monitoring) it should cover?</i> – <i>How can OSNL support the openness of AI models, including documentation, licensing, provenance, metadata, and reproducibility? And what should model openness mean?</i> – <i>How can OSNL coordinate with national and international AI policy bodies (e.g. those implementing the government’s generative AI vision) to align open science and AI governance?</i>
<p>10 Minutes</p> <p>Capture perceived missed opportunities and underemphasised stakeholder groups, as well as potential recommendations for inclusion.</p> <p>Guiding question: Do stakeholders think there are any priorities the program has missed so far?</p>	<p>In the OSNL self-reflection we read that some stakeholders feel smaller institutions or applied-sciences sectors were underrepresented in OSNL’s first cycle.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – From your expertise in Open Research across the globe, are there themes, priorities, or stakeholder groups you think were missed or underemphasised in the OSNL priorities? – How do you think OSNL could solicit and integrate feedback on missing priorities in preparing the next work programme? <p>Possible follow-ups:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – <i>Are there domain-specific priorities (e.g. open education, open hardware, equity/DEI) that stakeholders would like OSNL to include more strongly?</i> – <i>In stakeholder feedback, were there surprises or ‘wish list’ areas you did not expect — how will OSNL evaluate whether to incorporate them?</i>
<p>Closing</p>	
<p>5 Minutes</p> <p>Capture any additional comments participants would like to address.</p> <p>No guiding question.</p>	<p>Are there any other comments you would like to share with us before we invite the Covenant Partners to join us?</p>
<p>Invite Covenant Partners to join the group</p>	

Annex 3: List of interviewees

Name	Affiliation
Alenka Prinic	Universiteit Leiden
Anita Eerland	Radboud Universiteit
Anna Paron Cabanero	Universiteit Leiden
Antica Culina	Nederlands Instituut voor Ecologie
Antonio Schettino	Erasmus Universiteit Rotterdam
Björn Bartholdy	Technische Universiteit Delft
Bogdana Huma	Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam
Dagmar Eleveld-Trancikova	RadboudUMC
Darco Jansen	Universiteiten van Nederland
Dirk Verloop	Ministerie van Onderwijs, Cultuur en Wetenschap
Florian Schubert	Universiteit Twente
Franciska de Jong	Universiteit Utrecht (emerita)
Frederike Schmitz	Open Science NL
Han van Krieken	ZonMw
Hanne Oberman	Universiteit Utrecht
Hans de Jonge	Open Science NL
Jeroen Sondervan	Open Science NL
John Doove	SURF
Just de Leeuwe	Technische Universiteit Delft
Kristina Korshunova	Technische Universiteit Eindhoven
Leon van Ekeren	Avans Hogeschool
Lex Bouter	Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam (emeritus)
Maartje Zweers	Promovendi Netwerk Nederland
Madeleine de Smaele	4TU.ResearchData
Margaret Gold	Universiteit Leiden
Marianne de Laet	Koninklijke Nederlandse Academie van Wetenschappen
Marjan Grootveld	Data Archiving and Networked Services
Mark van Assem	Open Science NL
Marta Teperek	Open Science NL
Martijn Kleppe	Koninklijke Bibliotheek
Martijn van der Meer	Promovendi Netwerk Nederland

Name	Affiliation
Martine de Vos	Universiteit Utrecht
Martine Pronk	Liber Europe
Mohammad Gharesifard	Rijksuniversiteit Groningen
Nicole Emmenegger	Data Archiving and Networked Services
Niklas Hohmann	Universiteit Utrecht
Olga Minaeva	NWO-Instituten
Peter-Bram 't Hoen	Radboud UMC
Ron Augustus	SURF
Ruben Kok	Health-RI
Sander Bosch	Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam
Sanli Faez	Jonge Akademie
Santosh Ilamparuthi	Technische Universiteit Delft
Sarah Coombs	Saxion Hogeschool
Sonja Meeuwssen	Leiden UMC
Thed van Leeuwen	Leiden Universiteit
Viola Woeckel	Erasmus MC
Willem Scholten	Erasmus Universiteit Rotterdam

Annex 4: Key achievements of Open Science NL in its formative years (2023–2025)

1. OSNL as a national catalyst for Open Science

OSNL has rapidly established itself as a uniquely positioned organisation in the Dutch research ecosystem: a national catalyst for Open Science that combines independence, system-level coordination, and an ability to innovate at speed. Launched in 2023 as a “regieorgaan” hosted by NWO but operating with a distinct mandate, OSNL was designed to accelerate the transition to Open Science by doing what no individual institution could achieve alone: providing national direction, removing structural barriers, and enabling coordinated, collective action across the entire knowledge system.

From the outset, OSNL has demonstrated an unusually high degree of agility and creativity in the way it supports the field. Its mandate allows it to widen eligibility, design non-competitive and trust-based funding instruments, and mobilise communities around shared priorities — features that many stakeholders highlighted as essential to overcoming fragmentation and sustaining momentum. Operating with a compact programme office, OSNL has managed to convene researchers, support staff, infrastructures, and institutions in ways that feel both system-aligned and community-driven. The organisation’s two-year programming cycle, informed by broad consultations and expert advisory panels, has enabled it to translate national ambitions for Open Science into concrete, accessible, and strategically coherent instruments (OSNL, 2025).

The review found that OSNL’s configuration as a ‘regieorgaan’ naturally brings tensions: some covenant partners expressed a desire for more influence over strategy or project selection, or greater decentralisation of authority. Yet the evaluation committee concluded that this model is precisely what has allowed the Netherlands to make more consistent and integrated progress on Open Science than many comparable countries. Where other systems struggle with siloed or mandated-driven approaches, OSNL’s coordinating role has enabled coherence, reduced duplication, and given the national Open Science movement a visible centre of gravity.

Despite significant budget cuts, OSNL has maintained programme continuity and strategic coherence, supported by compensatory funding from NWO and an efficient operational structure. Throughout its first two years, OSNL has demonstrated that coordinated, high-trust, and innovative funding models can drive culture change at scale. Its early achievements indicate that it is not merely an implementing body, but a system shaper — a platform through which Dutch research institutions collectively redefine what Open Science looks like in practice, and how it strengthens the resilience and quality of the knowledge ecosystem.

2. The first work programme (2024–2025)

The inaugural 2024–2025 programme deliberately cast a broad, foundational net across five clusters, capacity building, Open Science infrastructure, robust research processes, evidence for Open Science, and empowering communities, to address both the technical and cultural requirements of the transition. Prioritisation balanced the urgency of resolving bottlenecks with the maturity of initiatives ready for immediate implementation in relation to the NPOS 2030 Rolling Agenda

2.1 Capacity building

The National Training Platform for Research Data Professionals responds to a structural skills gap: international benchmarks recommend roughly three FTE data professionals per 100 researchers, while Dutch institutions report as few as one FTE serving 100–500 researchers. The platform is designed to develop an accredited,

baseline curriculum and to deliver sustained training across career stages, connecting with local and thematic Digital Competence Centres (LDCCs/TDCCs) and relevant networks. It is funded via a European tender and budgeted at €4.8 million for a single, four-year project. Complementing this, the Strengthening DCCs initiative invests in people and interoperability. It adds trainer and community-manager capacity to LDCCs, deploys domain-specific metadata and ontology experts within TDCCs, and appoints a national coordinator at the Netherlands eScience Center to lead a train-the-trainer programme for open research software. Together, these investments amount to €15.3 million over four years. A competitive call for Citizen Science Hubs seek to professionalise and institutionalise citizen science and societal engagement through five regional hubs, each co-developed by universities and universities of applied sciences and aligned nationally through Citizen Science Nederland (CS-NL); the four-year budget is €2.0 million. Finally, a targeted grant of €0.3 million supports institutional open publishing, strengthening non-profit, diamond-OA capacity and networking among emerging university presses and library-led publishing initiatives.

2.2 Open Science infrastructure

The Open Science Infrastructure programme provides inclusive support for tools, platforms, workflows, and services spanning open access, FAIR data and software, citizen science, and reproducibility practices. Projects emphasise interoperability and sustainability, aligning with the federation ambitions of EOSC and national efforts such as Publinova and the Netherlands Research Portal. Eligibility includes Dutch knowledge institutions ('kennisinstellingen') and support organisations (SURF, eScience Center, National Library, Health-RI). One competitive round took place for a total of €17.5 million. The budget was subsequently increased to €35 million.

2.3 Robust research processes

The Replication Studies programme revives and broadens a successful NWO/ZonMw initiative (2016–2019) and responds to KNAW's call to fund replication more systematically. A competitive, discipline-inclusive call offers awards between €75k and €250k for projects up to two years, totalling €5.2 million. In parallel, the Research Software Sustainability programme recognises the centrality of software in modern research by funding community-driven enhancement and maintenance. Delivered through the Netherlands eScience Center, the programme provides €5.4 million for strengthening long-term reusability, quality assurance, and transparent research outputs.

2.4 Evidence base for Open Science

OSNL's evidence strategy begins with an open call for Research on Open Science (up to €250k per project and four-year duration; total €2.8 million) to study barriers, solutions, and the effects of interventions and policies, from recognition and rewards to open peer review and dataset reuse. This includes a tendered co-creation trajectory call on Designing participatory citizen science which aims to map legal, procedural, and practical pathways to equal partnership for citizens and intermediaries toward a dedicated NWA call (budget €0.1 million, 1-1.5 years). Finally, OSNL pilots a national Monitoring & Evaluation framework capable of combining robust quantitative indicators with qualitative measures of behaviour, barriers, and practice change (€0.4 million over two years).

2.5 Empowering communities

Community mobilisation is central to OSNL's culture-change theory. The Open Science Festival, attended by the evaluation committee, continues as a national flagship, convening researchers, support staff, and policy-makers, with €100k per year (2024–2025) to ensure free attendance and broad participation. A rolling, first-come-first-served Open Science Meetings scheme provides micro-grants to grassroots groups, enabling rapid exchange around practical topics and emerging needs (€300k per year). OSC-NL, the national network of local Open Science

Communities, receives a non-competitive grant to professionalise coordination and embed local branches sustainably (total €0.4 million for 2024–2027, building on €0.65 million to local OSCs in 2023). CS-NL, the national citizen science network, is similarly funded to consolidate and expand practitioner support and cross-community collaboration (€1.1 million, 2024–2027). To align incentives, OSNL also funds institutional implementation plans integrating Open Science into hiring and promotion, awarding €50k to each participating institution and €150k to national coordination (total €1.4 million).

3. The second work programme (2026–2027)

The second programme shifts from establishing broad foundations to targeted consolidation and sustainability, with five themes, infrastructure, capacity building, empowering communities, incentives, and monitoring & evaluation, explicitly mapped to the five culture-change levers (“make it possible, easy, normative, rewarding, required”). Its development combined advisory-panel input and broad community consultations (including during the 2024 Open Science Festival), while responding to the ministerial budget reduction partially offset by NWO.

3.1 Infrastructure

The Open Science Infrastructure call becomes more targeted. Building on exceptionally high demand in 2024, OSNL focuses on prioritised, widely shared needs; stimulates collaboration and interoperability; balances domain-agnostic tools with discipline-specific services; and aims for a success rate of at least 25%, consistent with NWO’s organisational strategy. A total of €17.5 million is scheduled for 2027, with mechanisms to coordinate consortia and reduce duplication. In parallel, OSNL tackles a persistent bottleneck: access to sensitive data. A national coordination and implementation track provides expertise and alignment across domains, while 28 implementation grants of €50k build a critical mass of early adopters. The budget phases €1.1 million in 2026 and €1.4 million in 2027, recognising the effort needed to harmonise policies and practice around standards such as ODRL and GA4GH passports/DUO.

3.2 Capacity building

Capacity building in 2026–2027 extends beyond skills and roles to long-term sustainability and cross-pollination of expertise. OSNL proposes a short, focused training programme on infrastructure sustainability that combines strategic competencies (governance, finance, stakeholder engagement) with best-practice technology and long-term planning. This initiative recognises that resilience depends on more than technical excellence and addresses the gap observed in many community-run services; its budget is €250k in 2026. In the same year, OSNL introduced a mobility and development scheme for open-science professionals. Instead of a single, centralised training track, the scheme funds structured study visits, up to €25k each, enabling individuals or teams to learn in context from peers, hosts, and international counterparts. Applicants commit to articulate learning objectives, a concrete programme with host engagement, and provide a plan to embed and disseminate outcomes within their home organisations and the wider community. The rolling, first-come-first-served design, budgeted at €1.0 million, is intended to be accessible and practical. Recognising the rising importance of open research hardware, OSNL proposes a four-year national network to raise awareness, train practitioners, connect diverse communities (from labs to citizen science), and coordinate with adjacent national and international networks. This is the first such initiative in the Netherlands and is budgeted at €1.5 million in 2027. Capacity building for citizen science also continues: a second round of Citizen Science Hubs is planned for 2027 and builds on the initial cohort with mentoring support from established hubs, strengthening professionalisation and balanced regional coverage; the budget is €2.5 million. Finally, OSNL initiates a mapping exercise on AI and Open Science. Rather than producing another set of tools or guidelines, the assignment consolidates community concerns, questions, and needs; maps existing resources and expertise; and identifies gaps, culminating in recommendations for the field and for OSNL’s future programming. This procurement has a budget of €150k in 2026.

3.3 Empowering communities

Community empowerment mechanisms continue and expand. The Open Science Festival remains the annual flagship event under OSNL's direct management, free to attend, and budgeted at €100k for both 2026 and 2027. The Open Science Meetings scheme, proved popular and effective, grows to €400k per year, providing timely support for small, community-led events that surface needs, share practice, and connect initiatives across institutions and regions.

3.4 Incentives

Incentive structures are refined to convert effort into tangible, reusable outputs. A new Making Research Outputs FAIR scheme offers small, first-come-first-served grants (up to €50k) for applicants to make FAIR-compliant high-value but under-used or non-FAIR outputs, including sensitive datasets, essential software lacking documentation, hardware designs, AI models, and non-traditional outputs. Applicants document steps taken and commit to share lessons with the community, raising the overall quality and reusability of outputs; the 2026 budget is €2.85 million. The Replication Studies programme returns in 2027 with operational refinements to assessment, such as exploring distributed peer review, while ensuring disciplinary breadth; eligibility excludes 2025 awardees to widen participation. The 2027 budget is €3.0 million.

3.5 Monitoring & evaluation

The Open Science Monitor proceeds from framework to infrastructure. Building on recommendations from phase-one work and aligned with UNESCO's Open Science Monitoring Initiative and CoARA, OSNL intends to fund a multi-year project (most likely via an EU tender) to develop a sustainable, transparent, inclusive monitoring and evaluation infrastructure for the Netherlands. The 2027 budget is €1.0 million, with an emphasis on mixed-methods measurement that can capture not only outputs but changes in behaviour, practice, and systemic barriers. Programme lines include implementation and assessment costs; the total across both years is €36.4 million (€7.55 million in 2026 and €28.85 million in 2027).

4. OSNL self-reflection (2023–2025)

The evaluation committee carefully considered the OSNL self-reflection and assessed it to be honest and realistic. Inclusion of elements of the self-reflection here indicates our endorsement.

The self-reflection aimed to prepare for the external evaluation and assesses OSNL's progress against relevance, coherence, efficiency, and early indicators of effectiveness, while summarising accomplishments across OSNL's core tasks. OSNL anchors programming in the NPOS 2030 Ambition and Rolling Agenda and uses systematic community engagement to ensure that priorities match evolving needs. The first programme drew directly from NPOS without an extra consultation (to avoid delays), whereas the second programme was shaped by workshops at the 2024 Open Science Festival, advisory-panel discussions in late 2024, and Steering Board deliberations in early 2025.

4.1 Evolution from the first to the second work programme

The 2024–2025 programme built foundations:

- capacity through a national training platform and strengthened DCCs.
- communities via OSC-NL, CS-NL, the Festival and Meetings
- core instruments such as infrastructure, replication, and software sustainability.
- a pilot for monitoring and evaluation.

In 2026–2027, OSNL pivots to targeted consolidation and sustainability. The infrastructure call is more focused and aims for higher efficiency and success rates. New micro-grants help make diverse outputs FAIR, translating small investments into widely reusable artefacts.

System bottlenecks receive concentrated attention: access to sensitive data is harmonised through a national coordination track and a critical mass of implementation grants; infrastructure resilience is supported through practical training. OSNL also introduces open research hardware and AI & Open Science as emerging priorities identified by consultation.

Meanwhile, community momentum is reinforced through continued Festival support, expanded Meetings budgets, and a mobility programme for professionals. Finally, monitoring advances from a pilot framework to a national infrastructure. This shift aligns with the fiscal context, ministerial cuts partly mitigated by NWO, and reflects an evidence-informed, consultative transition from “build broad foundations fast” to “deepen, interoperate, and sustain what works,” increasing the probability of durable cultural change and European alignment.

4.2 Coherence

Internationally, OSNL’s breadth, covering open scholarly communication, FAIR data, open research software, and citizen science/societal engagement, matches the UNESCO and European committee conceptions of Open Science. The Netherlands Commission for UNESCO described OSNL’s programme as among the most progressive worldwide. OSNL’s staff and leaders are active in CoNOSC, CoARA, RDA, ReSA, EOOSC, and ORE, drawing on global good practices such as POSI and Invest in Open Infrastructure pilots.

Nationally, OSNL maps agendas with UNL and SURF and complements NWO’s TDCC network, for example by funding interoperability expertise. Non-competitive support for OSC-NL and CS-NL helps embed communities locally and coordinate nationally. Internally, the mapping onto five culture-change levers avoids siloing and clarifies contribution pathways; this becomes explicit in the 2026–2027 programme.

4.3 Efficiency

A lean programme office operates within a 6% overhead cap and leverages NWO’s established processes and support departments. Instrument design balances rigour, speed, collaboration, and administrative load, using a pragmatic mix of competitive calls, non-competitive awards, rolling grants, direct grants, and tenders. The first programme’s success rates reflect design choices: Citizen Science Hubs were scoped to front-runners (~56%), Replication Studies sits near the desired 25–35% zone (~35%), while the inclusive infrastructure call led initially a ~12% rate and after the NWO budget increase to a success rate of 25%, intentionally surfacing demand and needs for the targeted round in 2026–2027.

4.4 Early indicators of effectiveness

OSNL commissioned CWTS and Dialogic (mid-2025) to develop a monitoring framework and prototype dashboard that go beyond simple output counts to include behavioural change, barriers, and qualitative impacts. Quantitatively, fifteen instruments were launched; by end-2025 approximately 218 projects will be awarded totaling €72.4 million; the 2024 infrastructure call drew 174 pre-proposals; advisory-panels met eighteen times; the Steering Board met thirteen times; the Strategy Council met seven times; and communications and festivals reached and engaged large audiences with strong satisfaction. Qualitatively, enthusiasm and commitment are rising, with UNL and SURF integrating Open Science into strategies; feedback praises inclusivity, notably OSNL’s eligibility for research support staff and outreach to smaller and Caribbean institutions; and international interest in instruments such as Recognising & Rewarding Open Science is evident.

4.5 Challenges and lessons

Two risks require ongoing attention. First, sector-wide budget pressures may hinder institutional embedding and long-term sustainability of funded initiatives, even with NWO's compensation; leadership alignment in the Strategy Council and Covenant Partners remains vital. Second, noting that administrative duties must remain proportionate to the 6% overhead norm, this cap constrains OSNL's ability to invest time in substantive engagement and coordination work and was a concern to the evaluation committee. We understood the interest in increasing NWO support beyond administrative tasks with additional in-kind capacity.

4.6 Accomplishments by core tasks

OSNL's four core tasks have been substantially progressed. Funding and implementation have awarded approximately 218 projects by end-2025 with €72.4 million in total, using instrument designs that reduce burden and improve efficiency. Monitoring and evaluation moved from concept to commissioned framework and dashboard development with mixed-methods metrics. Knowledge sharing is embedded through advisory panels and a sustained communications and engagement footprint. Strategic coordination via the Strategy Council has provided a forum for national-level dialogues on open access, EOSC, and infrastructure needs.

Annex 5: Short biographies of the evaluation committee members

Paul Wouters (committee chair)

Paul Wouters is an emeritus professor of scientometrics at Leiden University and a leading figure in the study of research evaluation, scholarly communication, and the use of performance indicators. He previously served as Dean of the Faculty of Social and Behavioural Sciences, as Director of the Centre for Science and Technology Studies (CWTS) and as director of the Virtual Knowledge Studio (KNAW). His work spans the history of citation indexing, the sociology of metrics, and the influence of evaluation systems on research cultures.

David Sweeney

David Sweeney CBE is Professor of Research Policy at the University of Birmingham and one of the United Kingdom's most influential research policy leaders. He was the founding Executive Chair of Research England within UKRI, where he oversaw national research funding and the development of a healthy research and knowledge-exchange system. Prior to this, he directed Research, Innovation and Skills at HEFCE and played a central role in shaping and implementing the Research Excellence Framework (REF). His earlier career includes leadership roles at Royal Holloway, University of London.

Henriikka Mustajoki

Henriikka Mustajoki, PhD, is a leading architect of Finland's national Open Science policy, which is co-created independently by the research community. As Secretary General of the National Open Science Coordination, she guides the co-creative national strategy development, stakeholder engagement, and the integration of open research practices across the Finnish research system. Her work emphasizes transparency, community-driven coordination, and sustainable implementation. Her research experience is on research ethics and collective decision-making.

Noémie Aubert Bonn

Noémie Aubert Bonn, PhD, is a postdoctoral researcher at Hasselt University and research associate at the University of Manchester, specializing in research assessment, research culture, research integrity, and open research. Trained originally in cognitive neuroscience and psychiatry, she shifted her focus to the systemic pressures shaping academic work. Her doctoral research examined how research assessments influence integrity and research practices. She has contributed to European projects, including SOPs4RI, and continues to work on responsible research practices and supportive research environments.

Robert van der Vooren (committee secretary)

Robert van der Vooren is an independent policy analyst and research consultant based in the Netherlands, specializing in Open Science policy, research assessment, and the governance of national research infrastructures. His work focuses on synthesizing complex stakeholder perspectives, evaluating large-scale policy programmes, and supporting evidence-informed decision-making across the Dutch and European research landscape. He has contributed to analyses of the National Programme Open Science (NPOS), sector-wide coordination initiatives, and institutional Open Science strategies.

Published: March 2026

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19130486>

Dutch Research Council (NWO)

Visiting address:

The Hague location

Laan van Nieuw Oost-Indië

2593 CE The Hague

Netherlands

Utrecht location

Winthontlaan 2

3526 KV Utrecht

Cover image: credits Shutterstock

Dutch Research Council | [NWO](#)

